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Deliverable 1.4 - Blueprints from the three pilot regions

Closing the gap between fork and farm for circular nutrient flows

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

B2B	Business-to-Business
B2C	Business-to-Consumer
B2G	Business-to-Government
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
CEDEX	Centre for Studies and Experimentation in Public Works
CJEU	Court of Justice of the European Union
CMC	Component Material Category
CLP	Classification, Labelling and Packaging
D	Deliverable
DM	Dry Matter
EU	European Union
ESG	Environmental, Social, and Governance
FPR	Fertilising Products Regulation
GE	Goldeimer
GVA	Gross Value Added
IBC	Intermediate Bulk Container
JRC	Joint Research Centre
K	Potassium
KIT contents)	Kompost aus Inhalten von Trockentoiletten (compost from dry toilet contents)
M	Month
N	Nitrogen
NPK	Nitrogen-Phosphorus-Potassium
P	Phosphorus
P.E.	People Equivalent
PFAS	Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances
PFC	Product Function Category
OMP	Organic Micropollutants
RD	Royal Decree
R&D	Research and Development
REACH	Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals

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RMP	Risk Management Plan
ROI	Return Of Investment
ROS	Return Of Sales
SDS	Safety Data Sheet
SE	Stakeholder Engagement
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprise
S360	Sanitation360
TD	TouchDown
TN	Total Nitrogen
TP	Total Phosphorus
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UDDT	Urine Dry Diverting Toilets
UV	Ultraviolet
UWWTD	Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive
VN	VunaNexus
WP	Work Package
WRP	Water Reclamation Plant
WWTP	Wastewater Treatment Plant

1 Executive summary

The focus of this deliverable is to produce blueprints towards a complete innovative circular model for nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) flows in the three pilot regions on Gotland (Sweden), the North German Plain (Germany) and La Axarquia region (Spain).

The development of these blueprints is part of Task 1.3 “Blueprints towards circular N & P flows” and directly linked to Objective 1.3 of Work Package 1 “Definition of pathways for technology uptake and implementation of circular N & P flows”.

The elaboration of the blueprints and specific subchapters included in this report has followed a co-design and co-implementation process in collaboration with other Work Packages (WPs) in P2Green. The expertise from various project partners and the knowledge gained throughout the project has been fundamental to providing accurate and well-founded data about the different pilot regions.

Participatory sessions and workshops organised by different WPs in P2Green (e.g., stakeholder awareness workshops, focus group interviews, cross-fertilisation workshops, etc.) have been designed to collect feedback from external stakeholders and identify barriers and drivers, adequate incentives, policy and regulatory reforms, needed alliances, etc. which are integrated in the blueprints. Operational aspects linked to the barriers identified are also included in the blueprints, including logistics for transport and collection of by-products, economic incentives, training needs, synergies with other innovators, social acceptance, governance aspects and the potential of replication in other sites.

These blueprints have defined the role of different actors and provided strategic insights to create an enabling environment for the market uptake of the project innovations, as well as for the implementation of governance schemes that underpin circularity of N & P flows.

A cornerstone of the blueprints has been the consultation with local stakeholders (e.g., tech companies, authorities, researchers) in order to integrate their views into the report.

This deliverable will serve as a reference document to produce specific communication and dissemination materials at a later stage of the project (in collaboration with WP6 partners). Visually attractive brochures with blueprints per pilot region will be created and uploaded to the “P2Green Innovation Platform” and will be distributed to key stakeholders from the pilot regions and beyond.

2 Introduction

Developing blueprints for the three pilot regions is a pivotal component of the P2Green project, as it lays the groundwork for a holistic and replicable circular nutrient flow system that connects urban waste streams with rural agricultural production.

The blueprints are comprehensive strategic documents that integrate the roles and responsibilities of a diverse range of stakeholders — from farmers and local authorities to technology providers. By clearly mapping out the operational pathways and logistical frameworks, these blueprints provide critical insights into the establishment and scaling of innovative systems that transform human sanitary waste into safe, bio-based fertilisers.

They are designed to address the multi-dimensional challenges of circular economy implementation by outlining technical processes, economic incentives, regulatory considerations, and social acceptance strategies. In doing so, the blueprints serve as both a diagnostic tool to identify potential barriers and as a guide for overcoming them through tailored, region-specific solutions. They facilitate stakeholder engagement and cross-fertilisation of ideas across the pilot regions, thereby ensuring that best practices and lessons learned are systematically incorporated into the governance frameworks.

Ultimately, the development of these blueprints is fundamental for achieving the project's overarching goal of closing the nutrient cycle—reducing reliance on mineral fertilisers, protecting natural resources, and fostering a resilient, sustainable food production system across Europe. This integrative approach not only enhances the technology readiness level (TRL) of the implemented solutions but also paves the way for their replication in other regions, amplifying the environmental, economic, and social benefits on a broader scale.

This deliverable (Chapter 3) begins with a comprehensive overview of the current state of play in the three pilot regions: Gotland (Sweden), the North German Plain (Germany), and La Axarquía region (Spain). It presents an analysis of the baseline scenarios that justify and incentivise the implementation of the innovative solutions and the development of circular value chains. It provides a concise characterization per pilot region of the environmental and socio-economic context, the current transformation of human sanitary excreta into safe bio-based fertilisers, the prevailing regulatory and institutional frameworks, key regional stakeholders, and the principal drivers and barriers influencing the adoption of circular approaches.

Following the assessment of the initial conditions, the pilot region pathways are illustrated (Chapter 4), from the inception of the P2Green project to the present stage (M30, May 2025). These pathways outline the sequential steps undertaken by each pilot region to conceptualise, design, establish, and commence the operation of the proposed innovative solutions and circular value chains. Additionally, the analysis

integrates insights gained throughout the implementation process, including challenges encountered, key actors involved, and significant findings emerging from the pilots.

In contrast, drawing upon the pilot region pathways and accumulated experiential knowledge, Chapter 5 includes the blueprints for the implementation of circular N and P flow models within the three pilot regions and replication in other regions. These blueprints are developed through contributions and expertise from various WPs and serve as a foundational guide for replication. The integration of key lessons and findings from the pilot regions is particularly crucial in facilitating the adoption of P2Green's approach by follower regions and local stakeholders. This chapter further explores essential enabling factors for the implementation of circular N and P flow models, including the establishment of strategic alliances, the role of key actors, the formulation of appropriate incentive structures, and the development of effective governance mechanisms.

3 State-of-play per pilot region

Chapter 3 presents an overview of the initial conditions in the three pilot regions - Gotland (Sweden), the North German Plain (Germany), and La Axarquia (Spain) - providing a baseline analysis that serves as a foundation for the implementation of the innovative solutions within the P2GreenN project (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1: Aspects considered to determine the state-of-play per pilot region

This chapter examines, amongst other aspects, the environmental and socio-economic characteristics of each region (subchapter 3.1), highlighting key factors such as climate conditions, land use patterns, agricultural practices, and demographic trends that influence nutrient management and resource recovery potential.

A crucial component of this baseline assessment is an evaluation of current human sanitary waste production in each region (subchapter 3.2), including quantitative data on generation, treatment processes, and existing nutrient flows. The chapter further explores the extent to which these nutrient streams are currently utilised, outlining prevailing challenges and inefficiencies in conversion processes and bio-based fertiliser production. Additionally, the existing regulatory and institutional frameworks governing nutrient management and circular economy practices are listed (subchapter 3.3), identifying potential barriers and opportunities for policy integration.

Beyond technical and regulatory aspects, the key actors involved in nutrient management within each region are identified and mapped (subchapter 3.4), including public authorities, wastewater treatment operators, farmers, and other relevant stakeholders. Their roles, interests, and levels of engagement provide critical insights into the enabling conditions necessary for the transition toward circular value chains.

Chapter 3 concludes with a summarised list of the identified drivers and barriers for the uptake of the project innovations in each of the pilot regions (subchapter 3.5).

By outlining the baseline scenarios in each pilot region, this chapter underscores the urgent need for innovative solutions that close nutrient loops, reduce dependency on mineral fertilisers, and mitigate environmental impacts. The analysis presented herein serves to justify and incentivise the adoption of circular approaches, demonstrating how tailored strategies can address region-specific challenges while contributing to broader sustainability goals.

3.1 Environmental and socio-economic characterisation

➤ Swedish pilot region

The Swedish pilot region is situated on Gotland, an island located in the Baltic Sea. As an island economy, its low self-sufficiency threshold, summer droughts and sea level rise), a largely seasonal economy, difficulties in attracting high-skilled labour and limited administrative capacities (OECD, 2022).

The island has the second largest agricultural sector out of all Swedish regions, with 35% of its surface covered in farmland (Marken I Sverige, n.d.). Winters are mild, wet and windy and summers are hot and dry. With an annual average of 530 mm of rainfall, Gotland has experienced multiple droughts in recent years (Isgren & Speckhahn, 2019). This has led to the implementation of multiple water saving technologies on the island, such as desalination to purify seawater for drinking purposes. In tandem, there is widespread use of on-site sanitation systems at homes, such as compost- and urine diverting toilets, creating an environment fitting for nutrient recycling (Isgren & Speckhahn, 2019).

Gotland also lies in a “dead zone” of the Baltic Sea, caused by nutrient pollution leading to eutrophication and temperature increase (Vigouroux et al., 2021) (see **Figure 2**). For example, small and municipal wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) in Sweden discharge > 15,000 tons of N per year, which accounts for approximately 30% of the total anthropogenic N emissions from Sweden (Havs- och Vattenmyndigheten, 2022). Therefore, the HELCOM's Baltic Sea Action Plan *inter alia* envisages the reduction of nutrient inputs from wastewater (HELCOM, 2021). On Gotland, especially old and partially non-functioning decentralised WWTPs are a major problem, together with high seasonal peaks of nutrient loads from tourism. The discharges from the facilities affect both the groundwater and the surface water, and thus new solutions are needed to improve N & P retention.

Figure 2: Gotland surrounded by algal blooms in 2019 (Copernicus Sentinel data, European Space Agency, 2019)

Gotland's economy is mainly built upon the public sector, which contributes to 26% of gross value added (GVA), as well as transport and trade (18.2%). The remaining sectors contribute to no more than 10% of GVA, consisting of industry (9.9%), real estate (7.9%), general services (7.4%), construction (7.4%), manufacturing (6.8%), agriculture, forestry and fishing (6.1%). Gotland's economy also relies heavily on its small- and medium-sized companies (SMEs) that hold a large share of national exports amounting to 60% in 2018. This led to Gotland being ranked second in 2018 out of all regions in terms of SME development, demonstrating the importance of SMEs for the island (OECD, 2022).

As an island, Gotland can benefit from not having to integrate issues into larger infrastructure elements, making local choices for water, sanitation, fertilisers and broadband more flexible. In terms of fertilisers, Gotland produces a part of its own need thanks to the large livestock industry, enabling manure to be used by many farmers (Parfitt, 2023). Despite this, mineral fertilisers are still required to meet agricultural demand, and Sweden's lack of domestic production makes farmers dependent on imports (Niléhn, 2022).

Sweden imports approximately 750,000 tons of fertilisers annually (RISE, 2024). For Gotlandic farmers, prices are especially high and sensitive due to the need to transport it from the mainland onto the island, and farmers experienced a large fluctuation in prices during COVID-19 and still due to Russia's invasion of Ukraine (Alexander et al., 2022). This puts Sweden at high risk during geopolitically uncertain times, especially in terms of N access, due to mineral fertilisers comprising the majority of N supply to the soil.

Therefore, the Swedish government tasked the Swedish Board of Agriculture to identify Swedish initiatives that could help support domestic fertiliser production and circulate the existing resources from Swedish industries. These include waste from mining, ashes, biogas digestate, food waste, urine and more (Jordbruksverket, 2023). Sanitation360 (S360) is mentioned as one of 18 initiatives and is the only company recycling urine and was of high interest due to being an N-based fertiliser. This makes P2Green's work, scaling-up urine recycling on Gotland, especially important for Sweden's fertiliser security and circularity goals.

➤ German pilot region

The two facilities of the German pilot region are located in the federal states of Lower Saxony (faecal composting) and Brandenburg (urine treatment). Both are agricultural states, large in size and relatively low densely populated with 165 P/km² and 85 P/km² respectively. Whilst the area of P2Green field trials at the Lüneburg Heath in Lower Saxony is one of the largest livestock producers in Europe and as such is a net exporter of nutrients, Brandenburg and the Barnim region are net importers.

Whilst the Lüneburg Heath receives a maritime climate by the Atlantic Ocean, Barnim has a continental influence with lower annual precipitation (450–600 mm). Nevertheless, drought is an inclining challenge in both regions. In Barnim, summers are typically warmer and winters colder than in the Lüneburg Heath. Lower Saxony accounts for approximately 47% of Germany's total irrigated agricultural area (Total: 554,000 ha, Brandenburg: 30,900 ha) (Statistisches Bundesamt, n. d.). Both areas are predominated by sandy soil, with low natural fertility and high permeability, leading to nutrient leaching (Duggan et al., 2025).

Only 64% of groundwater bodies used as the main drinking water resources are in good chemical status, primarily due to excessive nitrate pollution (see **Figure 3**) (Umwelt Bundesamt, 2017). The pilot region's groundwater bodies are in poor chemical status and the nitrate quality limit of 50 mg/L is exceeded in 27% of the country's groundwater bodies. The regions are hydrologically connected to the Elbe River (Lüneburg Heath) and the Oder River (Eberswalde), draining to the North Sea and the Baltic Sea respectively.

Figure 3: Chemical status of groundwater bodies in Germany based on assessment from 2016. Marked in yellow are the locations of the P2GreenN pilot sites in Ollsen (square) and Eberswalde (circle) (German Environment Agency, 2017)

➤ Spanish pilot region

The Spanish pilot region of La Axarquía, in the autonomous region of Andalusia, is characterised by a Mediterranean climate with hot, dry summers and mild, wet winters. The region has undergone significant demographic and economic changes over recent decades. Its population has grown from approximately 143,000 inhabitants in 1998 to over 220,000 inhabitants by 2021, with an additional 50,000 seasonal residents during peak tourist periods (Hurtado et al., 2024). Agriculture remains the backbone of the local economy, particularly the cultivation of subtropical fruits such as avocados and mangoes. The area dedicated to these crops has more than doubled since 1999, reaching nearly 9,500 hectares by 2021. La Axarquía region now produces around 90% of Spain's mangoes and 70% of its avocados, with most of it directed for European export markets. However, this agro-industrial growth has placed enormous pressure on local water resources. Traditional sources, including La Viñuela reservoir, have become insufficient, with reservoir levels dropping to critically low levels in the recent years—only 16.4% of capacity in May 2022 (Cabezas, 2022).

The reliance on irrigation in La Axarquía is crucial for maintaining agricultural productivity, yet diminishing water availability threatens long-term sustainability, particularly for subtropical crops like mangoes and avocados, which now account for

76% of total agricultural water use (Hurtado et al., 2024b). The growing need for resilient solutions has led to the exploration of reclaimed water as an alternative source for irrigation. In fact, the Andalusia government has invested over €42 million in expanding reclaimed water infrastructure, ensuring a total of 19.14 hm³ of reclaimed water for irrigation (AxarquiaPlus Editors, 2023). Beyond agriculture, tourism is another significant economic sector, benefiting from the region's natural landscapes and subtropical climate, further increasing water demand. Seasonal consumption due to tourism is 60% higher than the daily national average (Cabezas, 2023). This situation becomes particularly critical during summer months, coinciding with the peak tourist season and the lowest water reservoir levels of the year. Specifically, the historical minimum capacity of the La Viñuela reservoir was recorded in July 2023, when it reached 8.9% of its total capacity (Cabezas, 2023b). However, the competition for water resources between tourism, urban development, and agriculture further underscores the urgency of implementing efficient water reuse systems to ensure the region's socio-economic sustainability, preserving freshwater resources for urban (domestic) use during critical periods.

On the other hand, the area where the Spanish pilot is located, was classified as "Vulnerable zone to Nitrate Pollution" due to over-fertilisation with N-based chemical fertilisers, which has damaged the quality of groundwater aquifers (see **Figure 4**).

Figure 4: Vulnerable zones (purple colour) to Nitrate Pollution in La Axarquia region (MITECO, n. d.)

Restrictions on the use of such fertilisers are in place, and this classification remains valid, with the last review conducted in 2020. This emphasizes the urgent need for sustainable agricultural practices to protect water bodies' quality.

3.2 Human excreta use and conversion into safe bio-based fertilisers

As described in D1.6 (Progress in set up of pilot regions)¹, between 2005–2012, the nutrient load to European seas was 3,300–4,100 kt N/y and 260–300 kt P/y (Grizzetti et al., 2021). The majority of these are derived from mineral and manure fertilisers (71% N and 93% P). Together with atmospheric depositions (17% N), these can be considered the major diffuse inputs from human activities, whereas industrial and domestic wastewater (3,5% N and 5% P) are the major pollution contributors to the accumulation of nutrients in European waters. The European Zero Pollution Action Plan targets to deliver a ‘near-zero water discharge’ of pollutants.

The numbers of nutrients discharged from WWTPs vary greatly between countries. In Sweden, total nitrogen (TN) emissions amount to 51 kt N/y (Naturvårdsverket, 2021). Simultaneously, 33% of the N load and 16% of the P load Sweden emits to the Baltic Sea is derived from municipal wastewater (Jordbruksverket, 2022). In Spain, WWTPs receive approximately 67 kt N/y, out of which 73% (49 kt N/y) is discharged into water bodies with the WWTP effluent (Mayor et al., 2023). In Germany, thanks to wide application of tertiary treatment, the effluent contains only 19% of the received N, but the specific annual per capita load of N discharged annually is comparable to that of Spain (see **Table 1**).

Table 1: Nitrogen release data for each pilot region’s country

Pilot region / parameter	Annual N release total (kt N / y)	Annual N release specific (kg N / capita·y)	Annual N release to water bodies (kt N / y)	Share of agriculture (of N release to water bodies) (%)	Share of wastewater (of N release to water bodies) (%)	N from wastewater cumulated (kt N)
Sweden	51	5.0	15	47 %	33 %	13.7
Germany	1,547	18.3	585	79 %	14 %	106.0
Spain	913	18.8	779	93 %	6 %	47.0

Data from SRU, 2015; Tuholske et al 2021; Naturvårdsverket, 2021; Jordbruksverket, 2022; Mayor et al., 2023.

High nutrient concentrations from human sanitary waste streams are ultimately released to rivers and coastal zones. Nutrient removal in WWTPs is very energy intensive and in modern WWTPs not all N can be removed from wastewater (Tuholske et al., 2021). The removed N is ultimately ending up in the atmosphere as molecular nitrogen (N₂) and to a lower share (~ 1%) as the very potent greenhouse gas nitrous oxide (N₂O) (Foley, 2015). For P, only 34% of WWTP inputs are recycled by spreading sewage sludge on agricultural fields. The use of sewage sludge for fertilisation, however, is connected to

¹ Beneker, González, Parfitt, Senecal, D1.6 rev1, Progress in set up of pilot regions, 2024, P2Green consortium.

problems such as pharmaceuticals, heavy metals and novel entities (e.g. PFAS), which are rarely removed by WWTPs (Gianico et al., 2021).

From the total amount of approximately 40 billion m³ of wastewater treated in the EU annually, approximately 10 million tonnes of sludge (DM) derive. How sludge is treated across Europe also varies greatly from country to country. Whilst Germany incinerates most of its sludge already today, Spain and Sweden are mainly applying it to land (Eurostat, 2020). Looking at field application, improvements in management and application are needed to reduce the large amounts of nutrient losses through gas emissions, leaching and runoff. In the past, high levels of heavy metals in sludge for agricultural use were an issue in terms of their negative impacts on both soil and human health. Even though these levels have decreased up to 10 times within the EU, partly due to the EU's Sewage Sludge Directive: Council Directive 86/278/EEC, heavy metals in sludge still pose a threat to our food system (European Commission, 2023). The presence of PFAS in sludge is also a growing concern, potentially leading to the contamination of food (EEA, 2023).

➤ **Swedish pilot region**

In Sweden, the Federation of Swedish Farmers (LRF) recommended in 1999 that their members stop using sludge because of concerns about its quality, a recommendation that many farmers still follow to this day. A study by Wallenberg & Eksvärd (2018) found that 85% of Swedish farmers who are offered to use sludge decline, mainly due to worries about traces of hazardous substances in the sludge. Despite this, Sweden's use of sludge has increased in recent years and in 2020, 34% of treated sewage sludge was recirculated back to agricultural land (SOU, 2020). This is largely thanks to the work of a WWTP certification called REVAQ which strictly limits the number of pathogens and heavy metals that sludge can contain to be allowed as a fertiliser (Eurofins, n.d.). However, REVAQ-certified sludge is only permitted for use in conventional farming (SOU, 2020).

Households and various industries across 419 urban areas in Sweden produce wastewater equivalent to 12.8 million population equivalents (p.e.) daily—roughly 2.56 million cubic meters (European Environment Agency, 2025). Sweden collects wastewater from approximately 12.8 million p.e. Of this, 12.6 million p.e. undergo biological treatment, and 11.6 million p.e. receive advanced treatment with N and/or P removal. The difference arises because 0.22 million p.e. of wastewater—discharged from smaller urban areas (under 10,000 p.e.) into coastal waters—does not require biological treatment, as permitted under EU legislation when environmental protection is ensured (however this is changing with the new Wastewater Directive). Similarly, N and P removal is only mandatory for larger agglomerations discharging into sensitive areas, explaining why this applies to a smaller volume than the total collected (European Environment Agency, 2025).

Sweden has a long history of innovation in the source separation and reuse of human excreta, with urine-separating systems introduced as early as the 1970s. The initial motivation was to simplify the collection and management of faeces, which contain most pathogens (Johansson, 2000). In the 1990s, the first porcelain urine-diverting toilets were developed, representing a key advancement in making source separation more user-friendly (Johansson, 2000). Interest in these systems grew steadily throughout the decade, alongside increasing motivation to reuse urine as a fertiliser (Johansson et al., 2009) (see **Figure 5**).

By 2006, more than 10,000 porcelain urine-diverting toilets had been installed across Sweden, and at least 10–15 large-scale systems for human urine reuse were in operation—many managed by municipalities (Johansson et al., 2009).

Figure 5: Brief overview of the history of urine-diverting toilets in Sweden from 1988 to 2000 (Johansson, 2000)

Despite these early gains, the expansion of urine-diverting systems began to slow in the early 2000s. A lack of economic incentives and a missing market infrastructure for decentralised sanitation hindered further development (Johansson et al., 2009). The small volumes of urine available made it economically unviable for farmers to invest in dedicated storage and handling systems (Johansson et al., 2009).

Households also faced practical challenges with the toilet systems themselves. The front bowl—designed to collect urine—was susceptible to blockages caused by hair, toilet paper, faeces, and urine precipitates, often leading to unclean appearances (Johansson, 2000). These issues were particularly problematic in public settings (personal experience and informal discussions).

In addition to technical issues, there were systemic barriers to widespread adoption. When urine is separated at source, the responsibility for its management falls on the toilet or building owner. Local municipalities typically do not provide logistical or financial support. Although urine separation reduces N & P loads on WWTPs, owners of urine-

diverting toilets continue to pay standard wastewater treatment fees—on top of their own storage, transport, and handling costs.

Bengtsson and Tillman (2004) underscore the need for technical solutions to be matched by supportive administrative infrastructures and legal frameworks to ensure societal acceptance. In the absence of such enabling conditions, the installation of urine-diverting toilets lost momentum. Still, Sweden currently has more than 22,000 urine-diverting flush toilets and over 150,000 urine-diverting dry toilets—primarily in summer cottages, with around 15,000 flush models in permanent residences.

Interest in urine-diverting toilets and source separation is resurging, driven by increased investment in innovative sanitation solutions. Advances are being made on both the front-end (toilet design) and back-end (urine treatment and nutrient recovery technologies). The main challenge to scaling up urine recycling remains at the back-end. Urine's high-water content makes transport and storage costly, particularly when transferring it from urban areas to agricultural land. EOOS Next and Laufen have both stressed the need for compact, cost-efficient technologies that concentrate nutrients at source (personal communication). Various urine treatment technologies are in development to produce fertilisers from source-separated urine (Antonini et al., 2012; Harder et al., 2019; Randall & Naidoo, 2018; Tilmans et al., 2015; Udert et al., 2015; Vinnerås, 2002; WHO, 2014). For an overview, see Martin (2020)—note that while the report is in French, Chapter 2 is in English and offers a useful summary. However, despite decades of research, many of these innovations remain confined to laboratories and pilot projects, struggling to reach commercial scale (Larsen et al., 2009; Maurer et al., 2006; McConville et al., 2017). This highlights the importance of P2Green and the need to support the pilot regions.

Sweden's experience with urine source-separation provides valuable lessons for the broader European Union, particularly in the context of the European Green Deal, the Circular Economy Action Plan, and the revised Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive (UWWTD). These frameworks place increasing emphasis on resource recovery, nutrient recycling, and reducing environmental pollution from wastewater.

Moreover, the EU Fertilising Products Regulation (EU 2019/1009) provides a legal pathway for the safe use of bio-based fertilisers derived from human excreta, provided they meet established safety and quality criteria. This creates opportunities to support Member States in advancing circular nutrient strategies that align with EU climate, soil health, and biodiversity goals.

In support of these goals, the Swedish government is currently defining milestone targets for nutrient recycling from wastewater. As of 2021, national objectives aim to recycle at least 15% of N and 50% of P from wastewater streams for food production by 2030 (Finnson, 2021). The government is also considering mandatory nutrient recycling quotas for mineral fertilisers (Finnson, 2021). Achieving these targets will almost certainly require the inclusion of urine recycling, which offers a highly concentrated, low-

volume nutrient source. Compared to an average wastewater volume of 140 litres per person per day, urine accounts for only 1.5 litres per person per day—yet contains the majority of excreted N and P.

➤ German pilot region

In Germany, households and certain industries in 3,913 urban areas generate 111.3 million p.e. of wastewater every day (WISE, 2025), which is an equivalent to 22.25 million m³. The urban wastewater is treated in 8,659 WWTPs across the country, with a 94.5% volumetric rate of treatment, with N & P removal, before it is discharged (Wilke, 2025). Operators must apply biological (secondary) treatment with N & P elimination, so that at least 70% of the TN is removed from the wastewater and maximum 2 mg/L of P remain in the effluent generated (Abwasserordnung, 1997). For 1.8 million p.e. of wastewater, Germany applies individual systems (e.g., domestic treatment plants; septic tanks) with usually lower treatment targets, mostly in remote areas and small communities below 2,000 inhabitants.

In Germany, the novelation of the sewage sludge ordinance (AbfKlärV, 2017) limits the field application of sewage sludge significantly. By the year 2029 (> 100 k p.e.) and by 2032 (>50 k p.e.) respectively, WWTP operators are obliged to recover P from sewage sludge. As the field application can in most cases not be matched with the new thresholds on pollutants, the mainstream path taken is the mono-incineration of sewage sludge, whilst only a small number of municipalities is exploring the struvite path (cf. Project “Phosphor-Recycling in the heathlands and the Harz mountains”)², or source separation. Exceptions to the obligation to recover P exist for sewage sludge with low P concentrations (less than 20 g P per kg of sewage sludge (dry matter)).

The collection and treatment of separated urine and dry toilet contents has the potential to reduce the inputs of N and P into the sewer and thus reduce the pressure on wastewater utilities to recover P from sewage sludge.

Significantly reducing the per capita load of N also, source separation approaches would additionally reduce the pressure on the Elbe and Oder River basins, which flow into the North Sea and Baltic Sea, respectively. Instead of fertilising water bodies, with the P2Green solutions, the nutrient can be applied where needed – on farmland. Urine-based fertilisers can contain high N-concentrations to improve crop growth. With faecal composting, human nutrient resources can be converted into carbon-sequestering fertilisers to improve the health and nutrient storage capacities of degraded soils in Brandenburg and the Lüneburg Heath in Germany to thereby enhance the resilience of the regional agri-food-system.

Event toilets are typically rented by the event owner, whilst GE provides service free of charge for the event producer but charging the end users. Urine Dry Diverting Toilets (UDDT) for use as event toilets must be serviced closely to guarantee user acceptance

² Phosphor-Recycling in der Region Harz und Heide. <https://p-net.tech/>

and thereby result in higher fees compared to conventional chemical mobile toilets. Municipalities like Darmstadt are equipped with their own fleet of UDDT for the provision of temporary sanitation service to regional events. UDDTs for use as public toilets typically require significantly less investment costs due to the unnecessary of establishing sewer and drinking water connections, making them an attractive applied solution to cities such as Leipzig, Cologne, Berlin or Eberswalde.

➤ **Spanish pilot region**

In Spain, urban wastewater treatment and reuse are regulated by strict national and EU laws, including the Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive and Regulation (EU) 2020/741 on minimum standards for agricultural reuse. The country generates around 63.1 million p.e. of wastewater daily, treated in 1,829 WWTPs, 1,046 of which remove N & P — key drivers of eutrophication (WISE, 2025b).

Spain reuses approx. 10% of its treated municipal wastewater, equivalent to around 400 million m³/y (Malinauskaite, 2024). The reclaimed water is mainly used in agriculture and landscaping. By 2022, 60% of reclaimed water was used for agricultural irrigation, 10% less than the national average (INE, n. d.). This figure underscores the country's commitment to circular water use, especially in the face of increasing water scarcity.

Currently, 87% of Spain's urban wastewater complies with EU standards, including nutrient removal, required mainly for discharges into sensitive areas. Eutrophication remains a concern where treatment is insufficient, as seen in La Axarquia region.

Andalusia, one of Spain's most water-stressed regions, has significantly scaled up its water reuse efforts. As of 2024, the volume of reclaimed water reached 70 million m³/y, representing 17% of the region's total water use (González, 2025). This reflects growing momentum toward integrating reclaimed water into broader water resource management strategies.

In La Axarquia, wastewater is processed in conventional WWTPs, often without nutrient recovery. However, due to growing water scarcity and environmental stress, circular water use is gaining relevance. The ongoing water crisis has led to the rapid implementation of reclamation infrastructure in La Axarquia so that approximately 80% of local wastewater is already treated and reused, which is complemented by the import of reclaimed water from the nearby city of Malaga (Hurtado et al., 2024b).

In this context, the P2Green project aims to transform municipal wastewater from WWTPs into bio-based fertilisers, using nutrient-rich effluent for fertigation in avocado and mango farming.

3.3 Regulatory and institutional framework

This subchapter has been elaborated in collaboration with WP3 (SUSTCHEM, NUIM UCD, NUID) and highlights significant regulations and strategies in force.

Relevant work on these frameworks has been undertaken within D3.7 (Scoping review of the legal frameworks submitted November 2023) and D3.8 (Legislative Report – being undertaken currently and due in M36). Most of the relevant legal regimes have a foundation in EU law but are then implemented and enforced domestically (with some areas requiring further development). D3.7 and D3.8 focus on the core areas of relevance, e.g. waste, reclaimed water, fertilisers, environmental protection, mutual recognition etc. (with some variation on focus points from D3.7 to D3.8). A key issue that has become apparent in the research is that the legal regimes do not clearly and adequately address P2Green activities and products, with it being challenging to identify what elements apply or potential avenues that would enable commercialisation. This becomes relevant for law reform considerations (flagged briefly in subchapter 5.5 below).

Key overarching EU policies include:

- The EU Green Deal and related documents such as the Circular Economy Action Plan, outlining key ambitions for the EU regarding efficient resource use, a robust economy, addressing pollution and climate change, etc. Focus points include reform of agricultural policy, pesticides, waste etc. The EU Green Deal thereby provides significant motivation for, and reflects changes to, relevant EU legal regimes. Further changes are expected in the near future.
- Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) 2023-2027: As part of the CAP (2023-27) each Member State is required to present the Commission, for their approval, a National Strategic Plan supporting EU objectives and the Green Deal whilst responding to local needs. These include measures to support the environment and the climate and contributing to organic production.

While not hard law, the EU policies help shape and inform law, incentives, approaches etc. and are important to bear in mind.

Key EU waste laws include:

- Waste Framework Directive – overarching framework. Provides very expansive definition of waste (as interpreted by the CJEU). If waste is not legislated for under other EU waste law, it typically will fall back to be regulated under this Directive and usually will require a waste permit. Article 6 also provides for the potential for waste ceasing to be waste (must ensure specific conditions are fulfilled), under EU or national criteria or on a case-by-case basis nationally.
- (revised) Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive (UWWTD) – mandates connections to either individual or collection systems (for wastewater treatment) depending on population size. Mandates different treatments for discharges (e.g. into streams), but with some exceptions. No definition of ‘wastewater’, although insights available from other definitions. Unclear what the precise parameters of the legislation are, and arguably significant flexibility remains for the Member

States as a result. If human excreta is not regulated under the UWWTD, then it will be regulated under the Waste Framework Directive. This is complex and will be addressed further in D3.8.

- Sewage Sludge Directive – outdated legislation regarding the use of sewage sludge on agricultural land. It nonetheless can help provide relevant insights.
- EU Regulation 2020/741 (Water Reuse Regulation): Following treatment under the UWWTD, this Regulation establishes minimum water quality standards for agricultural irrigation using reclaimed water. Optional for Member States as to whether they permit the use of reclaimed water or not. They may also apply higher standards. Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2024/1765 aims to supplement the Water Reuse Regulation and focuses on the technical specifications of the key elements of risk management.
- Published documents to help implementation of the Regulation include a Technical Guidance for water reuse risk management by the JRC and Commission Notice Guidelines to support the application of the Regulation.

Other relevant regulations:

- Fertilising Products Regulation (FPR) 2019/1009: facilitates the placement of fertilising products on the EU market and thereby their use and sale across the whole of the EU. This includes products such as organic and organo-mineral fertilisers, soil improvers and inhibitors. If authorised, even if composed of ingredients that are considered waste under EU law, the product will be deemed to no longer be waste under EU law once the EU declaration of conformity is signed. The Regulation includes criteria regarding Product Function Categories (PFCs), Component Material Categories (CMCs), general environmental and human health standards, and a Conformity Assessment. For the PFCs and CMCs, there are varying requirements regarding origin, nutrient requirements, limits on contaminants, processing etc. These are detailed and complex. Currently, there is no obvious CMC that could cater for P2Green activities/products. The Regulation can be amended to add further CMCs.
- Organic farming Regulation 2018/848 sets out rules on organic production and the labelling of organic production. Such production is to contribute to the protection of the environment and the climate, maintain the long-term fertility of soils and contribute to a high level of biodiversity. General production rules are established and it restricts fertilisers to low solubility mineral fertilisers. The Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2021/1165 about authorising certain products and substances for use in organic production and establishing their list, includes fertiliser, soil conditioners and nutrients that may be used in organic production in Annex II. In the Annex stricter conditions for certain materials are outlined regarding eligibility for use or labelling—for example, farmyard manure originating from factory farming is excluded from use. The EU regulations on

organic farming seemingly do not facilitate the use of faeces, urine or products derived from these to be used in organic farming since these are not included in the list of permitted inputs for fertilisers, soil improvers, or nutrients. Reclaimed water is not considered a material input and is not explicitly addressed in the organic farming Regulations. However, its use may be allowed as an exception, provided it complies with all applicable EU and national legal frameworks, including those governing organic farming and water reuse.

- Regulation (EU) 2019/515 (Mutual Recognition): General starting point is that EU Member States should generally recognise the authorisation by another Member State of a product as if it had been authorised in its own territory. The Regulation provides a general framework for its operation, but it remains to be implemented by the Member States and each Member State may objectively justify not recognising the authorisation in another Member State, e.g. for environmental or human health reasons. Even where possible, the process, fees, timeline etc can vary significantly.
- Environmental law, including the Water Framework Directive, nature laws (e.g., habitats and wild birds directives, and the new nature restoration law). These are relevant, but largely indirectly and may depend on the specific location where the product is being tested or used.
- Regulation (EC) 1907/2006 (REACH) & Reg. (EC) 1272/2008 (CLP): as fertilising products are also chemical products, they must also comply with Regulation 1907/2006 on the Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH) and Regulation 1272/2008 on Classification, Labelling and Packaging of substances and mixtures (CLP). These are the two main regulatory frameworks that ensure a high level of protection of human health and the environment, as well as the free movement of chemicals in the EU's internal market. Neither Regulation applies to waste, but they do apply to substances that cease to be waste and more specifically to fertilisers. Both Regulations require a range of physical, chemical, toxicological and ecotoxicological data. The REACH Regulation aims to ensure a high level of protection against harmful substances, assess the safety of the chemicals used and enhance innovation and competitiveness in the EU internal market, while limiting the use of animal testing for the assessment of the hazards of substances. Registration is a key requirement. The FPR also sets additional REACH requirements for substances in fertilisers to further enhance the safety assessment of fertilisers - requirements referred to in industry as REACH+ (REACH plus). The CLP Regulation aims to identify the hazardous properties of substances or mixtures, classify them according to their physical, health and environmental hazards and communicate them to all economic operators via standardised formats through labels and Safety Data Sheets (SDSs).

For the individual pilot regions, the above laws will vary in relevance depending on the activities in question. However, largely they can focus on engagements with the domestic law once they bear in mind the relevant EU law. Some of the key laws are outlined here, but they will be developed and examined further within D3.8.

➤ **Swedish pilot region**

Sweden's legislative framework for nutrient recovery is influenced by both EU and national regulations – the former have been noted in the introduction to this section. As for national regulations, the most relevant are:

- SJVFS 2004:62 (regulations regarding environmental considerations in agriculture, including regarding the use of fertilisers).
- Environmental Code which, for example, sets quality requirements for recycled plant nutrients and end-of-waste criteria (based on the Waste Framework Directive).
- KRAV standards for organic production (linked to the EU law, but with further criteria).

In Sweden, the current regulatory landscape for the use of human urine as a fertiliser is characterised by uncertainty. There is no formal documentation or legislation that explicitly prohibits or permits using human urine in agriculture. Therefore, the practice exists in a legally grey area. Despite this, using human excreta in agriculture has a long-standing tradition in the country, particularly in rural areas where the use of source-separated sanitation systems is more common. In these contexts, farmers have been applying both urine and faecal matter - mostly in the form of treated sludge from WWTPs - for decades.

One regulatory framework of high relevance is the REVAQ certification system, a voluntary standard that WWTPs can apply for. If the REVAQ standards are met, the treatment plant gains approval to use their treated sludge for agricultural purposes in collaboration with local farmers. This system was developed in cooperation with the Swedish Water & Wastewater Association (Svenskt Vatten) and aims to reduce the presence of harmful substances in sewage sludge to ensure its safe in agriculture. Although REVAQ specifically targets wastewater sludge, it establishes a precedent for the use of recycled human-derived nutrients in agriculture. More information on REVAQ can be found at:

- RISE – REVAQ Certification
- Svenskt Vatten – Sludge Use and REVAQ

In the case of S360, the company has developed a novel approach to recycling urine by moving away from liquid and instead producing a dry, granular urine-based fertiliser. The production process involves ventilation and heat treatment to remove water and pathogens, leaving behind a nutrient-rich product containing plant nutrients such as N,

P, K, as well as micronutrients. Due to its novelty, both for the process and end product, it does not currently fall under existing regulatory frameworks for fertilisers or waste reuse.

However, there is currently a big focus on developing a more precise and efficient regulatory framework for the use of urine in Sweden. In another Swedish funded project (FORMAS), RECAPTURE (2022-2024), researchers from SLU and S360 (the P2Green pilot) as well as researchers from RISE and Ecoloop, investigated how to overcome the existing regulatory hurdles and help build a more circular fertiliser market.

The only relevant certification that existed for urine, called SPCR 178, was supposed to be discontinued in 2024 due to lack of use. The RECAPTURE-consortium revised the discontinued SPCR 178 to create a new certification, called “new SPCR 178”. It includes clear requirements to ensure both nutrient content and safety from potentially harmful substances in urine. The RECAPTURE project has also mapped the current regulatory obstacles for placing source-separated urine on the market and proposed a new certification system for recycled plant nutrients that both food producers and consumers are asking for.

The absence of clear regulatory guidance presents a challenge for innovations on the circular nutrient market. Efforts by actors such as S360, thanks to projects like P2Green and RECAPTURE, may serve as catalysts for the development of new policies, particularly as the demand for domestically produced and circular fertilisers increases.

Additional challenges are posed by the regulations regarding, for instance, the End-of-Waste status which S360 has not yet attained. Sweden has not created any relevant national criteria for End-of-Waste status and instead any operator must apply for an individualised decision based on the considerations derived from Article 6 of the Waste Framework Directive. Further, urine and urine-derived products were allowed in organic farming (and KRAV-certified farming) prior to EU membership and regulation, which is currently not the case. However, if the use of urine and urine-derived products were permitted under the EU law on organics, this would likely enable KRAV certification (provided other conditions were met).

➤ **German pilot region**

The key EU legislation noted above provides the broad frameworks within which Germany and the regions therein operate. The ambiguity within the EU waste legislation is especially pertinent and can be seen to impact on the domestic laws.

Key legislation includes the Federal Water Act (Wasserhaushaltsgesetz, WHG). § 54 of the WHG provides a very wide, flexible definition of wastewater that focusses on changes in properties of the water due to its previous use³. It also imposes obligations

³ Abwasser im Sinne dieses Gesetzes sind das durch häuslichen, gewerblichen, landwirtschaftlichen oder sonstigen Gebrauch in seinen Eigenschaften veränderte und das bei Trockenwetter damit zusammen abfließende Wasser

(and rights) on municipalities regarding wastewater treatment. Municipalities then provide the more localised implementation, with requirements (linked to the EU regime) regarding connections, licences, treatments, etc. General waste law operates in parallel and steps in where relevant (again, as with EU waste law), e.g. the German Circular Economy Act (Kreislaufwirtschaftsgesetz).

Other potentially relevant, but of varying applicability, domestic laws include the Bio-Waste Ordinance (BioAbfV) and Sewage Sludge Ordinance (AbfklärV 2017). Of interest, policy documents can and do impact on the implementation of such ordinances, meaning that these too need to be examined and reviewed.

Further, municipalities have their own statutes.

Domestic fertiliser law is also relevant here, including in particular the Fertiliser Act (DüngG) and the Fertiliser Ordinance (DüMV), including its Appendix 1. The Fertiliser Act outlines the general framework for fertilisers within Germany, noting the potential for national authorisation, mutual recognition was authorised in another EU Member State, or for EU certified fertilisers. The Fertiliser Act provides for the creation of Ordinances to implement these provisions. The Fertiliser Ordinance is the key Ordinance and addresses what inputs or ingredients are permitted within fertilisers, as well as the limits on certain nutrients, minerals etc. It contains limits on N and P. There are other laws, e.g. The Fertiliser Application Ordinance (DüV), that are more relevant at a later stage.

The relevant mutual recognition law for fertilisers is addressed as noted in the Fertiliser Act, §5. This enables the placement on the market were authorised in another Member State and where the product meets the requirements for protection against risks to human or animal health or the natural environment, as well domestic substances meet such requirements. This would indicate that they must comply with relevant criteria found in the Fertiliser Ordinance, e.g. regarding pathogens or nutrient limits.

➤ **Spanish pilot region**

Spain's legislative framework for water reuse and nutrient recovery is influenced by both national and EU regulations. Key legislative acts include:

- The EU Waste Framework Directive, UWWTD and Water Reuse Regulation (noted above).
- Spanish Royal Decree 1085/2024: Governs the legal framework for water reuse in Spain. The Royal Decree was published on 22.10.2024 and repealed the previous national law regarding water reuse (RD 1620/2007). The new RD aims to promote sustainable water reuse as part of an integrated water management strategy to address scarcity, climate change impacts, and environmental preservation, while aligning with the new EU Water Reuse Regulation and

(Schmutzwasser) sowie das von Niederschlägen aus dem Bereich von bebauten oder befestigten Flächen abfließende und gesammelte Wasser (Niederschlagswasser). Als Schmutzwasser gelten auch die aus Anlagen zum Behandeln, Lagern und Ablagern von Abfällen austretenden und gesammelten Flüssigkeiten.

contributing to Spain's circular economy and ecological objectives. It establishes stringent quality criteria and risk management protocols for different reuse purposes, which must be met before reclaimed water can be applied for uses like irrigation, industrial processing, or environmental preservation. Specific prohibitions apply, such as disallowing reclaimed water for direct human consumption, recreational bathing, and food-related uses unless an emergency arises.

The CEDEX - Spanish public body dedicated to civil engineering, construction and the environment – has published documents to help with the implementation of the Royal Decree and include the following: Model of Risk Management Plan (RMP) for Reclaimed Water (PGRAR), Proposed Risk Analysis and Management Sheets, Methodological Proposal for Health Risk Assessment, and Analysis Using a Multi-Barrier Approach. CEDEX is also working on publishing a document about Environmental Risk Assessment Methodology.

The Spanish pilot region in La Axarquía aligns with these frameworks, ensuring compliance while promoting circular nutrient recovery solutions.

3.4 Key actors in the region

In this subchapter, the identification of key actors has been performed in collaboration with WP3 (IRS) and WP4 (CBS). P2Green's stakeholder engagement (SE) process follows a community-led and co-creation approach. The SE process aimed to develop a set of community-led strategies to facilitate the process of engaging with local stakeholders and assist partners to develop the regional stakeholder network, which is required to operationalise P2Green's innovative systems solutions, so that P2Green creates the required wider impact across its pilot regions. More information and the detailed methodology on the SE process can be found in D4.3 (Stakeholder engagement strategies).

The initial stakeholder identification and mapping of relevant stakeholders on pilot level took place in January 2023 (M2). All project partners were asked to brainstorm relevant stakeholders across various sectors, including public authorities, SMEs/businesses, research/academia, NGOs, the general public, and others. In the second phase, partners from both pilot and follower regions were tasked with ranking these identified stakeholders. Mapped stakeholders were categorised as having low, medium, or high relevance based on their importance within the operational area and context of the pilot region:

- High relevance: Key stakeholders whose involvement is essential for the success of actions in the pilot regions (aim to actively engage and collaborate with these stakeholders).

- Medium relevance: Stakeholders who should be considered and engaged, although their impact on the project's success may be less significant (aim to engage with these stakeholders).
- Low relevance: Stakeholders who should be kept informed but are unlikely to be actively involved in project activities (aim to inform these stakeholders about project and pilot activities).

This workshop provided an overview of relevant actors to be engaged through the project. Based on this initial mapping a stakeholder database was developed and regularly updated for each pilot region (more information and detailed overview of listed stakeholders can be found in D4.3).

Throughout the project, the developed stakeholder database was continuously updated through input from pilot partners and desk research.

The list of key stakeholders has been complemented with outputs from the analysis of social acceptance (as part of Task 3.3 - Awareness raising & enhancing social acceptance), in which both pilot region partners and the stakeholders that participated in the focus group interviews and personal interviews also identified important actors.

In the following, we provide an overview of the initial mapping of stakeholders and a brief summary of highly relevant stakeholders in each pilot region (with re-evaluated relevance of stakeholders undertaken in 2025).

➤ **Swedish pilot region**

In the initial Stakeholder mapping for the Swedish pilot (in M2) overall 60 stakeholders were listed, out of which 19 were identified with high relevance (detailed overview in D4.3). Overview of stakeholders in the Swedish pilot region according to their relevancy and level of operation are represented in **Figure 6**:

Figure 6: Key actors in the Swedish pilot region based on initial stakeholder mapping workshop

In March 2025 (M28), the stakeholder database was re-evaluated. This re-evaluation puts particular focus on relevant stakeholders in the Swedish pilot regions which should be further engaged in the pilot activities:

General public:

- Gotlands Allehanda (GA): Local newspaper (*informed about Swedish pilot activities*).
- Göteborgs-Tidningen (GT): Local newspaper (*not engaged with pilot activities yet*).
- Sveriges Radio (SVT): National radio channel (*not engaged with pilot activities yet*).

NGO:

- Live Green (Sustainable Festival): innovative action for more sustainable music festivals (*informed about pilot activities*).
- Orientering national club (SOFT): The Swedish Orienteering Association consists of 550 associations (*informed about pilot activities*).

Additional relevant stakeholders in this category:

- Hushållningssällskapet: an association of agricultural advisors supporting both researchers and farmers.

Research and academia:

- VA-Guiden and VA Syd: Water and Wastewater Guide: member service for those who work with water and wastewater planning, stormwater and small sewers – *(active engagement of VA with pilot activities)*.

Additional relevant stakeholders in this category are:

- Research Institutes of Sweden (RISE): independent, state-owned research institute.

Public authority:

- Almedalsveckan: democratic meeting place for social issues in Sweden in Visby, 23-27 Jun 2025 *(active engagement with pilot activities)*.
- Gotland military *(informed about pilot activities)*.
- Region Gotland: Gotland regional authority *(not yet engaged in the pilot activities)*.
- Swedish military *(informed about pilot activities)*.

Additional relevant stakeholders in this category are:

- Environmental departments of municipalities (particularly Uppsala).

SME/ businesses:

- DANFO: toilet solutions for public environments *(informed about pilot activities)*.
- IKEA: global furniture store *(not engaged with the pilot activities yet)*.

Additionally relevant stakeholders are:

- Water Revival Systems (WRS): Sweden's leading consultancy service on issues concerning wastewater, stormwater, natural waters and landfill leachate.
- .
- Local and national farmers, who can potentially use the fertiliser.
- Copenhagen-Malmö Port: one of Scandinavia's largest port operators with an infrastructure customised for all types of vessels.
- Hyrtoaletten, Toabolaget and Touch Down: portable toilet companies for urine collection.
- Vaila AB: a consultancy working in the field of fertiliser production, renewable energy and environmental protection.
- Cinderella: a company that sells incineration toilets.

➤ **German pilot region**

In the initial stakeholder mapping (in M2), 72 actors were listed, out of them 25 actors with high relevance across all areas of operation. The following visual (**Figure 7**) illustrates the mapped stakeholders in the German pilot region according to their relevancy and level of operation (detailed overview in D4.3):

Figure 7: Key actors in the German pilot region based on initial stakeholder mapping workshop

Re-evaluation of stakeholder database was not carried out by the German pilot region yet. The key relevant stakeholders in the German pilot region are:

General public:

- Allotment gardens and horticulture projects.
- Farmers: E.g. Conversations with young farmer Hauke Witte about a new vision for the Vagtshoff involving regional sustainability and a space to innovate in different directions around agroecology, climate protection, local/regional value chains and local/regional community building.

NGO:

- Network for Sustainable Sanitation Systems (NetSan): Network of actors from academia & research, industry and general public for cross-sectorial knowledge exchange and collaboration. Every two years NetSan, together with the national

associations valoo (Switzerland) and RAE (France), organises an international Connect the Networks-Conference.

- 3N Kompetenzzentrum Niedersachsen Netzwerk Nachwachsende Rohstoffe und Bioökonomie e. V.: Center with focus on use of renewable raw materials and biomass.
- Ernährungsrat (Nutrition / food councils): For example, nutrition / food councils of Lüneburg, Berlin and Brandenburg
- Zuwachs e.V.: A community-led solidary agriculture in which the economic aspect is limited to a regionally closed trade in goods without financial profits.
- Calluna Festival: Music festival focused on sustainable developments and social encounters in the region of Lüneburg Heath.

Research and academia:

- Fraunhofer-Institut: Research institute, especially Fraunhofer institute for system and innovation research (ISI) and Fraunhofer institute for Environmental, safety and energy technology (UMSICHT).
- Leibniz-Forschungsnetzwerke: Research network with focus on research connection and acceleration.
- Relevant partner projects and research initiatives: For example, zirkulierBAR national project (zirkulierBAR, 2025), hort2thefuture EU project.

Public authority:

- Bauämter: District building authorities, especially in the north German plain such as Berlin, Harburg and Hamburg.
- Federal Ministries: Such as Bundesministerium für Umwelt, Naturschutz, Reaktorsicherheit und Verbraucherschutz (BMUV) and Bundesministerium für Ernährung und Landwirtschaft (BMEL).
- City of Eberswalde (municipality): The city offers ideal conditions for the German pilot site through its strong sustainability focus, reflected in Barnim County's zero-emission strategy (since 2008) and Eberswalde's climate protection plan (since 2013).

SME/ businesses:

- Finizio Future Sanitation GmbH (Finizio): Dry toilet provider and recycling service operator.
- Laufen GmbH: Sanitation infrastructure provider (toilet and urinal manufacturing).

- Urban future GmbH: Service providers for the public sector, the real estate industry and anyone who wants to develop a plot of land or property.

Additional relevant stakeholders in this category:

- The national market leader for conventional (i.e. chemical, without reclamation) mobile toilets has addressed an interest in the business approach but remains reluctant as long as the legal framework remains uncertain.

➤ Spanish pilot region

In the Spanish pilot, overall, 41 stakeholders were listed in M2, out of which 19 stakeholders were identified with high relevance. The following visualisation (**Figure 8**) shows an overview of the mapped stakeholders according to their relevancy and level (more details in D4.3).

Figure 8: Key actors in the Spanish pilot region based on initial stakeholder mapping workshop

In March 2025 (M28), the stakeholder database was re-evaluated. This re-evaluation puts particular focus on relevant stakeholders in the Spanish pilot region that should be further engaged in the pilot activities:

General public:

- Farmers and end users
- Consumers of crops

NGO:

- ASAJA: Young farmers association in Malaga (*actively engaged with pilot activities*)
- ASERSA - Asociación Española de Reutilización Sostenible del Agua: Water reclamation association (*not informed or engaged about the pilots activities*)
- Asociación Española de Productores de Frutas Tropicales: Subtropical crops association (*informed about the pilot activities*)
- Irrigation community of Algarrobo (*actively engaged in pilot region activities*)

Additional relevant stakeholders in this category:

- Communities of Irrigators (Comunidades de Regantes): Key actors in managing water distribution for agricultural purposes and potential adopters of reclaimed water for irrigation.
- Additional agricultural associations and cooperatives: Groups representing farmers and agricultural businesses interested in sustainable fertilisation practices.

Research and academia:

- CSIC - IHSM La Mayora: Institute for Mediterranean and Subtropical Horticulture (Spanish National Research Council) (*actively engaged in pilot region activities*).
- IFAPA: Andalusian Institute of Agricultural and Fisheries Research and Training (*informed about pilot region activities*).

Additional relevant stakeholders in this category:

- Additional environmental and research organisations: Institutions dedicated to water conservation, agricultural sustainability, and circular economy advancements.

Public authority:

- EMASA: public water authority (*actively engaged in pilot region activities*).
- Consejería de Agricultura, Ganadería, Pesca y Desarrollo Sostenible - Junta de Andalucía (AGAPA): Andalusian Agrarian and Fisheries Management Agency - Department of Agriculture, Water and Rural Development (*informed about the pilot activities*).
- Dirección General Infraestructura y Explotación del Agua - Junta de Andalucía: Directorate-General for Water Infrastructure (*informed about the pilot activities*).
- Municipality of Algarrobo (*actively engaged in pilot activities*).
- University of Malaga: Department of applied Economics.
- University of Cordoba (*actively engaged in pilot activities*).

- CAJAMAR (Las Palmerillas): leading technological center for intensive Mediterranean agriculture (*actively engaged in pilot activities*).

SME/ businesses:

- AGBAR Agriculture: Agricultural consultancy company (*actively engaged in pilot activities*).
- HIDRALIA: Operator of WWTPs (*informed about pilot activities*).
- IKOS Tech: Technical provider of crop and agricultural management (*informed about the pilot activities*).

Additional relevant stakeholders in this category:

- Local and national WWTP operators and managers: Entities responsible for the operation and maintenance of WWTPs, playing a crucial role in nutrient recovery implementation.

3.5 Drivers and barriers

A summarised list of the identified drivers and barriers for the uptake of the project innovations is included in this subchapter. While general drivers for the success of the innovations include, for instance, shared commitment and mission-drive approach, trust and collaboration, or securing funding, each region has identified a series of specific factors driving impactful innovation. This analysis has been supported by WP3 (IRS, TRANSITION) and WP4 (CBS).

➤ Swedish pilot region

In Sweden, the uptake of urine recycling is driven by a long-standing tradition of using different toilet fractions, such as urine and sludge, as fertilisers, strong engagement from local governments and farmer associations, and high regulatory trust in novel and circular economy initiatives. Key enabling factors include the potential of reducing dependency on imported mineral fertilisers through local production, the numerous industrial waste heat sources that could be harnessed for urine drying, and an increase in public awareness of sustainable sanitation and nutrient recycling. Nevertheless, significant barriers persist, such as limited public understanding of how food is produced, misconceptions regarding safety of urine-based fertilisers, such as concerns about high pharmaceutical residue levels. Additional challenges arise from competing with the lower costs of conventional fertilisers like synthetic products and animal manure, difficulties collecting sufficient volumes needed for fertiliser production, complex value chains, regulatory limitations, and the absence of well-established environmental certification schemes. Addressing these barriers through enhanced awareness, regulatory alignment, and scaling of urine collection and production capacities will be essential to facilitate broader implementation and acceptance.

Drivers:

- Historically, urine recycling/urine as fertiliser is very common.
- Waste heat utilisation for urine drying.
- Mitigation of transport impact: Locally produced fertiliser.
- Local governments are becoming strong supporters.
- Regulatory support: The Swedish government supports circularity, and there is a high level of trust towards the Swedish government.
- Streamlining of municipal regulation regarding collection.
- Economic governmental support internalising external costs, (e.g. applying a CO₂ tax to fertilisers, internalising the environmental costs of nutrient pollution in products that contribute to it, or subsidising technologies with lower impacts on CO₂ emissions, water use, or nutrient pollution).
- R&D funding from EU like the P2Green project.
- Recognition of avoided costs for treatment of urine in WWTPs.
- Green festival certification with focus on sanitation.
- Third party certification to increase perceptions of safety of fertilisers.
- Customer awareness about the potential of urine as fertiliser and the challenges in the current sanitation systems.
- Collaboration with multiple municipalities, such as Malmö and Uppsala.
- Strong collaboration and operational control over the value chain.
- R&D investments in the technology to further maturity.

Barriers:

- There is low awareness in society about how food is grown.
- Lack of proper knowledge about the differences of the processes of pesticidisation and fertilisation; (leading many to believe that urine is directly sprayed on crops or remains on them in some way, even when they have reached the grocery store).
- Presence of pharmaceutical residues in urine fertiliser despite lower levels than in most current fertilisers used in agriculture. However, some argue urine should be held to a higher standard and want full removal - the debate is ongoing.
- Price-competition against conventional fertilisers.
- Farmers perceiving risks when taking out hectares for bio-based fertilisers.
- Lack of volumes of collected urine to satisfy farmer demand requiring operational expansions.

- Large-scale production of fertiliser is needed to attract interest and buy-in from potential partners.
- Skepticism from brewery partners related to perceived safety and reputation risks of potential partners.
- Complexity of circular value chain requiring extensive commitment and high needs of coordination.
- Ineffective public frameworks favoring centralised solutions and with silo municipal departments.
- Lack of knowledge about nutrient recycling of potential partners in the sector.
- Lack of public and decision-maker awareness on negative environmental impact of N & P.
- Social perceptions of WWTPs as effective in removing N & P pollutants.
- National legislation on ownership of waste.
- Missing a well-suited environmental certification of the fertiliser.

➤ **German pilot region**

Drivers

- There is a high trust in bio/organic products, and high acceptance of sustainable production.
- Water pollution mitigation: Both in the Baltic Sea and North Sea the nutrient load can be reduced; hence algal blooms can be reduced.
- Water scarcity, water saving, ground water level are also issues seen to be addressed by dry toilets .
- NGOs are effective and supportive.
- Economic governmental support to reach price competitiveness (subsidies, CO₂ taxes and avoided costs payments).
- Infrastructure investments to support decentralised sanitation solutions.
- R&D funding from EU like the P2Green project.
- Recognition of avoided costs of treatment in WWTPs.
- Third party certification of fertilisers and compost.
- Research on the quality parameters of the fertiliser / compost.
- Trustful collaboration to allow sourcing of competencies across partners.

- Knowledge sharing to gain from partner experiences to improve operational processes.

Barriers

- Regulatory constraints preventing uptake by farmers.
- Price-competition against conventional fertilisers.
- Lack of urine/faeces volumes collected to satisfy farmer demand.
- Ineffective sewage legislation decreasing economic incentives of decentralised solutions.
- Missing established culture of using separated human excreta for fertilising purposes.
- Missing building guidelines favoring new processes of urine diversion and decentralised production of fertiliser.
- Insufficient legislation requiring human waste to be mixed with flushing water restricting the use of dry-toilets.
- High upfront investments with risky and lower ROI compared with historical market conditions.

➤ **Spanish pilot region**

Drivers:

- Water scarcity mitigation: The increasing demand for irrigation water necessitates the adoption of alternative sources like reclaimed water.
- Regulatory support: EU and Spanish policies promote circular economy models, encouraging nutrient recovery from wastewater.
- Agricultural demand: Farmers are seeking sustainable alternatives to mineral fertilisers, creating a market for bio-based fertilisers.
- Technological innovations: Advances in wastewater treatment and nutrient recovery enhance the feasibility of implementing these solutions.
- Economic incentives: The rising cost of conventional fertilisers increases the attractiveness of bio-based alternatives.
- Clear and supporting legislative frameworks.
- The emergence of new water strategies, nationally and on a municipal level.

- Economic governmental support – financial aid to support viability and enabling cost competitiveness of reclaimed water.
- Enabling water tariff frameworks supporting the use of reclaimed water and making it price competitive.
- Increased discharge taxes and fines.
- Subsidies for the use of reclaimed water.
- Promoting tertiary treatment facilities in WWTP.
- Regional investments in piping infrastructure.
- Securing easy access to legal permits for farmers wanting to use reclaimed water.
- R&D funding from EU like the P2Green project for technology maturation.
- User acceptance of reclaimed water / public awareness campaigns.
- Official label to underscore the reduced environmental and water footprint of the agricultural produce.
- Increased price of well water.
- Partnerships with public authorities or agrochemical companies, or industry groups.
- Close collaborations with mutual interests.
- Adaptability of the solution - flexibility to suit different farm types & crops.
- Knowledge sharing and exchange of expertise to drive innovation and learn from each others' challenges.

Barriers:

- Regulatory constraints: Strict legal requirements and lengthy approval processes may delay the deployment of nutrient recovery systems.
- Public perception: Social acceptance challenges regarding the use of bio-based fertilisers derived from human waste.
- Infrastructure limitations: Existing wastewater treatment facilities may require upgrades to support nutrient recovery at scale.
- Economic viability: The cost-effectiveness of bio-based fertiliser production compared to conventional mineral fertilisers remains a concern.
- Sectoral competition: Conflicts between agricultural, urban, and tourism water users can slow the implementation of reclaimed water solutions.
- Low technological maturity making engagement of public authorities difficult.

- Negative farmer perceptions on reclaimed water creating a feeling of being forced to use it.
- High costs of treatment and distribution reducing financial profitability.
- Inefficient water tariffing frameworks reducing economic incentives of water reclamation.
- Insufficient water quality (high levels of salinity) decreasing the quality of the reclaimed water.
- Vanishing interests of reclaimed water in periods without abnormal weather (requiring drought-periods to gain relevance among the public).
- Complex collaborations around water reuse (involving public authorities, local governments, private corporations, etc.).
- Farmers in remote locations not connected with sewage system.
- Time-consuming administrative procedures to obtain permissions for reclaimed water use.

4 Pilot region pathways

Chapter 4 presents a detailed account of the step-by-step process undertaken by each of the three pilot regions to plan, design, establish, and commence operations of their respective innovative nutrient recovery solutions. This chapter builds on the baseline analysis provided in Chapter 3 and transitions from the initial conditions to the concrete actions taken within P2Green to implement circular models for N & P flows.

Each pilot region's pathway is examined chronologically, documenting the most relevant milestones achieved from the start of P2Green (M1, December 2022) to M30 (May 2025). This process-oriented analysis includes key aspects such as securing permits and authorisations, addressing technical and logistical challenges, engaging relevant stakeholders, and integrating lessons learned throughout the journey. Special attention is given to the role of public authorities, technology providers, farmers, and other key actors in facilitating the transition toward a circular nutrient economy.

A detailed description of the technologies and circular value chains in each of the pilot regions is included in Deliverable 1.6 - Progress in set up of pilot regions⁴.

A key reference for this chapter is **Figure 9** previously introduced in Deliverable 1.6. This figure outlines the diverse nutrient recovery strategies explored within P2Green, setting the foundation for the blueprints in Chapter 5.

Figure 9: Overview of the four different approaches and technology partners in P2Green

⁴ Beneker, González, Parfitt, Senecal, D1.6 rev1, Progress in set up of pilot regions, 2024, P2GreenN consortium. Available at: <https://p2green.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/03/Set-up-operation-and-validation-of-Pilot-Regions-1.pdf>

The implementation pathways described in this chapter are aligned with these approaches, showcasing how each pilot region has adapted and operationalised solutions tailored to its specific environmental, regulatory, and socio-economic contexts.

To provide a clear and structured visualisation of the implementation journey, this chapter concludes with “timeline diagrams” per pilot region illustrating the major steps and decision points in the development of each region’s circular N & P flow model. By capturing the challenges, solutions, and insights gained along the way, Chapter 4 serves as a valuable resource for informing future replication efforts and optimising nutrient recovery systems across different regions.

➤ **Swedish pilot region**

The Swedish pilot is developing a circular system linking urine collection, processing, agriculture, and food production. Urine is collected from three hubs—Gotland, Uppsala, and Malmö—using a stabilising chemical to prevent N losses. In 2023, 6 m³ was collected on Gotland; by 2024, 11 m³ came from a single Uppsala event. The goal is to scale collection to 150 m³ by the end of the project. The pilot has also expanded its network by partnering with the municipality of Uppsala and toilet rental company Toabolaget.

On Gotland, urine is collected using portable urinals provided by TouchDown and processed by S360, which dries the urine using renewable energy. A second, portable drying unit—built in partnership with SLU—has been operational since May 2024. Connected to a cement factory to use waste heat, the system processes ~21 L/m²/day, reducing 250 L to 12 L of concentrate. N concentrations vary from 8% (festival urine) to 15% (household urine). SLU and S360 are testing ways to standardise N levels, aiming for a farmer-preferred 10%.

The concentrated urine is mixed with a bio-based binder to create a pelletisable material. Lab tests show similar N release rates to commercial NPK fertilisers (Aronsson 2024). Field trials led by Hushållningssällskapet showed promising yields: in 2023, barley fertilised with urine pellets and NPK both yielded 6,500 kg/ha, outperforming fresh urine (5,500 kg/ha) and unfertilised plots (4,500 kg/ha). However, the protein content (13%) exceeded brewing industry standards due to drought conditions. Gotlands Bryggeri brewed a trial beer but requested better irrigation to improve future barley quality.

Despite technical success, scaling faces regulatory, financial, and infrastructural challenges. Urine falls into grey legal zones and is often classified as waste outside public utility areas. Financial incentives are limited across the value chain, and production volumes remain too low to meet broader demand, though farmer interest is strong.

Following, some of the key developments for the pilot since April 2024.

First Commercial Customer

In July 2024, S360 partnered with Pastamakarna, a restaurant on Fårö using a urine-diverting toilet. S360 collects stabilised urine from an IBC tank, processes it, and uses it for fertiliser production. This pilot demonstrates a business model for small-scale enterprises.

Public Outreach & Education

In mid-2024, S360 hosted a public webinar with GreenTime, a sustainability initiative for events. The session explained how event organisers can reduce environmental impact through urine collection, raising awareness among scouts and music festivals.

For World Toilet Day (19 November 2024), S360 and Gotland's science centre Fenomenalen launched an interactive exhibit on circular sanitation, targeting children and young people to promote early engagement with sustainable systems.

Urinal Testing for Inclusivity

At a national wastewater conference in Uppsala (January 2025), S360 and SLU tested two urinals: a male Urimat model and a new unisex ceramic prototype designed by S360. User feedback led to design improvements, such as adding handlebars for squatting support. Additional trials are ongoing.

Launch of 'Kissamaja' Portable Urinals

S360 introduced yellow portable urinals named "Kissamaja" ("Pee-Maja"), a familiar play on "Bajamaja" ("Poo-Maja"), to ease public acceptance. These units, fitted with unisex urinals and mesh filters to prevent contamination, are designed solely for urine collection. An EU trademark application was submitted in April 2025. The Kissamaja units will debut during the Uppsala spring celebrations, attended by over 100,000 people.

Stadium-Scale Urine Collection (CiNURGi Project)

S360 and SLU are developing Sweden's first large-scale urine recycling system at Studenternas Stadium in Uppsala as part of the CiNURGi project⁵. Scheduled for installation in autumn 2025, it aims to collect enough urine during each football season to fertilise five football fields. A March 2025 trial during a match estimated that 1,500 litres could be collected per game at full capacity. The system will include on-site drying to reduce transport emissions.

Permit Preparation for Scaling Up

To support scaling, S360 is applying for two environmental permits—one each for facilities on Gotland and in Uppsala—as they transition from SLU operation to independent commercial ownership. Under Swedish environmental law, urine is

⁵ CiNURGi project <https://interreg-baltic.eu/project/cinurgi/>

considered non-hazardous waste, and drying processes fall under dewatering regulations requiring notification and compliance. A future permit application will also be required for a urine granulising facility.

Figure 10: Swedish pilot region pathway (own elaboration)

➤ German pilot region

The circular value chain of the pilot region in Germany consists of the three partners Kreiswerke Barnim, VunaNexus (VN), Goldeimer (GE) and is based on an interregional urban-rural transaction and divisional treatment of faeces and urine in two different locations of the North German Plain.

KWB is a regional recycling hub serving approximately 200,000 citizens in the county of Barnim and, as a company (GmbH), is fully owned by the county. Since 2019, in partnership with the private company Finizio, they facilitate a back-end solution for public and event dry toilets for the Berlin metropolitan region, reclaiming solid human waste from urban events and public city toilets at the scale of >250,000 people per year.

A pilot facility for processing dry toilet waste was set up at KWB's recycling site on the outskirts of Eberswalde.

In 2022 the Berlin city senate started a pilot project with 24 permanent public dry toilets operated in urban spaces. The material is collected by Finizio and recycled at the KWB premises. In 2023, KWB implemented a urine treatment capacity of max. 100 m³/yr in

cooperation with VN, which was complemented by a distiller unit in 2024 to produce the liquid fertiliser Aurin.

Obtaining building and operating permits from the local authorities have been challenging, as the intersectoral, discretionary powers of the authorities relating to different applicable legislation result in intensive and time-consuming coordination processes between the authorities. This has an impact on technical planning. Authorities have a duty to avoid risk for people, animals and the environment, and where the risk has not been clarified by law or technical directives, the legal and administrative requirements to safeguard all risk prevention measures are often system overarching whilst public administration is often limited to their pre-determined scope of singular (and linear) responsibility.

GE offers dry toilets to festivals, allotment gardens and off-grid nature tourism destinations. GE is providing 80 – 100 mobile toilets mainly to music festivals. In 2018 GE started a first large-scale composting trial at the premises of the AWR in Rendsburg-Eckernförde.

The Vagtshoff farm in the county of Harburg has been providing a material and logistics hub to GE since the year 2014. Due to the sandy soils of the farmland, the farm has been seeking sustainable solutions to regenerate the soil and improve its water and nutrient retention capacity.

Since 2024, GE realised a three-staged container-based composting facility for faeces to produce a quality assessed compost. The building permit for the composting facility was granted in 2024 by the local authorities.

In the German pilot region both bio-based fertilisers are applied in a combined way within field trials at Vagtshoff to produce rye and barley. The concept has been registered and acknowledged in 2023 based on DüMV §4 4/5 by the federal fertiliser authority.

Figure 11: German pilot region pathway (KWB & VN) (own elaboration)

Figure 12: German pilot region pathway (GE) (own elaboration)

➤ Spanish pilot region

The circular value chain of the Spanish pilot region consists of five partners, namely BIOAZUL, AXARAGUA, TROPS, CETAQUA and Agualytics (replacing the previous partner AgriSmart Data since December 2024) and is located in the municipality of Algarrobo (La Axarquía region, Málaga). Here, a circular water-nutrient solution – using a Smart Fertigation Tool - based on the reuse of treated municipal wastewater for the fertigation of subtropical crops is being demonstrated.

Pilot solution definition

Previous collaboration between some of partners had taken place before the start of P2Green (mainly for other R&D projects such as RichWater⁶ or Axarquía Sostenible⁷) but no contractual agreements had been established in the past. In 2022, P2Green formalised this relationship between the partners with a signed grant agreement.

The conceptual idea of the Spanish pilot region and development of the innovative solution was co-created and agreed upon between the partners involved in the proposal preparation of P2Green, with the main objective to continue and evolve from the work carried out by previous R&D projects on water reclamation use in agriculture - specifically in subtropical crops.

To continue with the research and innovation activities at the test site, the cooperation with the Municipality of Algarrobo and AXARAGUA (public water operator) was fundamental, authorising the use of their premises for R&D purpose until the end of P2Green (M48, November 2026). While the Water Reclamation Plant (WRP) operated by BIOAZUL is installed at the WWTP of Algarrobo - within the facilities of AXARAGUA – the plot where field trials with avocado and mango trees are located belong to the Municipality.

Field trials agreement and technical challenges

Decision and agreement on the selection of different fertigation treatments to ultimately calibrate and develop the Smart Fertigation Tool was a long process that took into account the size of the plot (850 m²), the final number of avocado and mango trees planted (120 in total), crop species selection, fertigation equipment installed, etc. while also replicating local farming practices in the region.

Shortly after the start of the field trials, initial campaigns revealed key agronomic and technical barriers. Reclaimed water showed high salinity (electrical conductivity - EC) due to seawater intrusion into the sewage system collecting municipal wastewater to the WWTP, resulting in higher levels of salinity in reclaimed water (EC > 2 dS/m). This resulted in phytotoxic effects on avocado trees treated with only reclaimed water, confirmed by foliar analyses conducted by TROPS. Even though the regional

⁶ RichWater project. European Commission. Grant agreement ID: 691402. <https://doi.org/10.3030/691402>

⁷ Axarquía Sostenible project. European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (FEADER). Contract n°: GOPG-MA-20-0002. <https://axarquiasostenible.es/>

government had committed to initiate renovation works of the sewage system, mitigation actions were implemented by pilot partners at the test site after noticing this issue, including dynamic dilution with local well water (usually 50:50 ratio) using a mixing unit and manual fertiliser dosing adjustments.

On the other hand, the secondary treated effluent from the municipal WWTP has also shown episodes of lower quality, especially after heavy rainfall episodes, with a negative impact on the water reclamation treatment and punctual presence of pathogens (i.e., *E. coli*). The good performance of the municipal WWTP is crucial for the quality of reclaimed water and constant communication with AXARAGUA is recommended.

Regulatory Alignment and Governance Maturation

The alignment with the EU Regulation 2020/741 and the new Spanish Royal Decree 1085/2024 on water reuse has been a core objective in the pilot. The implementation of the new water reuse regulation (RD 1085/2024) introduced in 2024 additional compliance requirements and considerations for the project (i.e., development of a Risk Management Plan – RMP), but no effect on the ongoing innovation solution or the reclaimed water quality.

AXARAGUA, with support from legal team in P2Green (SustChem, NUIM UCD, NUID) has drafted a tailored RMP including national guidelines for replication. At governance level, efforts are focusing on the development and testing of the RMP and the development of policy recommendations under the new RD 1085/2024.

Stakeholder Engagement and Strategic Alliances

Engagement with local authorities, research centres, farmers, and cooperatives, etc. has been supported by field visits, public events, and workshops. A close dialogue with the local irrigators has been crucial, as their adoption of reclaimed water for commercial production is seen as a success indicator for long-term replicability. In that sense, the stakeholder engagement workshop organised in M6 (May 2023) at the TROPS facilities marked a great milestone with considerable number of participants from La Axarquia region. The circular value chain and innovative solution under development was presented – drawing a lot of attention and interest from stakeholders present, who also provided valuable feedback on stakeholders to engage or unique selling points of the solution.

Smart Fertigation Tool validation

As part of the Smart Fertigation Tool (SFT), a beta version of the web-based application is available now, up and running since M28 (March 2025).

The development of the SFT was initially responsibility of the partner AgriSmart Data, a tech developer company part of the Spanish pilot region since the beginning of the P2Green project. Due to difficulties with progressing in the development of the SFT, this

partner was terminated and replaced by Agualytics, which is currently developing the SFT.

The next phase involves initiating the smart fertigation treatment, which will use reclaimed water with an optimised addition of mineral fertilisers – keeping into account the nutrient content in reclaimed water. Ongoing development of the algorithm for the SFT is in progress, with continuous improvements scheduled until M34 (September 2025). This iterative process aims to optimise the tool's performance and ensure its effectiveness in promoting sustainable and efficient irrigation practices.

Figure 13: Spanish pilot region pathway (own elaboration)

5 Blueprints for regional N & P flow circular models

Chapter 5 builds upon the implementation pathways described in Chapter 4 and synthesises the practical experiences of the three pilot regions into actionable guidance for the replication and scaling of the innovative circular nutrient flow models. Drawing on the contributions and expertise of several work packages (i.e., WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5), this chapter presents the blueprints for the deployment of circular models for N & P recovery and reuse in diverse regional contexts.

These blueprints integrate both the technical and socio-institutional dimensions of circular nutrient management, reflecting the lessons learned, challenges encountered, and solutions developed during the pilot phase. Particular attention is given to the drivers and barriers identified by each region, as these insights are critical for anticipating context-specific needs and opportunities in other regions. By weaving together regional experiences with cross-cutting thematic inputs from P2Green partners, this chapter aims to support follower regions in Italy, Greece, Hungary, and France —particularly local companies, start-ups, and public actors—in understanding and adopting the project’s circular approach.

To ensure clarity and usability, Chapter 5 is organised into a series of focused subchapters, each addressing a specific enabling aspect necessary for the successful implementation of N and P circular models. These include governance frameworks, stakeholder roles and responsibilities, technological configurations, economic and financial considerations, regulatory alignment, and strategies for social acceptance. As illustrated in **Figure 14**, this structure offers a comprehensive yet adaptable framework to guide replication efforts across diverse local and regional contexts.

Figure 14: Key enabling aspects included in the blueprints

Ultimately, this chapter serves as a practical tool and reference point, transforming project and pilots' knowledge into actionable pathways that can accelerate the transition to circular nutrient systems across Europe.

5.1 Role of key actors and needed alliances

This subchapter, prepared in collaboration with WP3 (TRANSITION) and WP4 (CBS), underpins the role of key actors (e.g., tech providers, farmer associations, building industry, etc.) that must be involved, as well as needed alliances and synergies with other innovators required to set-up and implement the circular models.

➤ Swedish pilot region

The implementation of the circular N & P flow model at the Swedish pilot region necessitates strong collaboration across multiple sectors (see **Table 2**).

Table 2: Key and supplementary roles, needed partners and alliances at the Swedish pilot region

Key roles	Responsibilities	Resources
Sanitation service provider	Urine collection	Urinals and urine diverting toilets, network of festivals and events
Technology provider	Treatment of urine into fertiliser	Urine drying system; Operating personnel; Urine drying system; Operating personnel.
Support from research institution	R&D-support, and to enable functional evaluation of the fertilising product	Scientists
Food-manufacturer	Close the circular nutrient loop and market the final product	Brewing capabilities; Farmer relationships
Supplementary roles	Responsibilities	Resources
Farming associations	Improved adoption and distribution	Existing networks for distribution and marketing of fertilisers.
Garden equipment retailers	Improved adoption and distribution	Distribution networks and provision of purchase channels.
Festivals	Collection and platforms for communication	Financial means to pay for services; Facilitation of urine collection in high-traffic locations.
Third-party organisations for trial evaluation	Increase trust related to functionality	Testing equipment and legitimacy
Local municipality	Coordination, institutional trust and beneficial legislative	Institutional trust and position to influence legislative interpretations related to waste management.

	interpretations related to waste management	
Needed partners / alliances	Responsibilities	Resources
Branch and business organisations (Svensk Vatten) (Swedish Nutrient Platform)	Enable support from wastewater utilities and increase awareness on N & P pollutants.	Institutional trust and communication channels.
Third-party certification providers	Verification of safety and communication of environmental benefits.	Legitimacy and customer evaluation channels.

➤ **German pilot region**

The following key and supplementary roles as well as the needed partners and alliances for the VN and KWB circular value chain are presented in **Table 3**.

Table 3: Key and supplementary roles, needed partners and alliances at the German pilot region (VN and KWB)

Key roles	Responsibilities	Resources
Sanitation service provider	Urine collection	Source separating toilets
Technology provider	Treatment of urine into fertiliser	Urine treatment technology Technical personnel Intellectual resources such as proprietary knowledge.
Building owner	Alternatively owner of physical premise undertaking waste management	Physical facility for permanent installation of urine treatment (alternatively container-based facility) In waste management case: Intellectual resources such as partnerships with sanitation provider and public authorities.
Supplementary roles	Responsibilities	Resources
Agricultural cooperations, chambers and consultants	Improved adoption and distribution	Existing networks for distribution and marketing of fertilisers.

Garden retailers	Improved adoption and distribution	Distribution networks and provision of purchase channels for B2C segments
Local farm for trial evaluation	Increase trust related to functionality	Agricultural land
Third-party research institute	Conduct trials and enable evaluation of performance	Scientific knowledge on crop cultivation Testing equipment
Needed partners / alliances	Responsibilities	Resources
Public water authorities	Integration with public framework	Ensure financial compensation for urine treatment
Building certification providers	Increased adoption of urine treatment technology	Established legitimacy
Legislative bodies	Ensure favourable legislation	Legislative power to promote use of fertilisers based on human excreta

The second pilot case is led by GE. Vagtshoff provides the area for the composting facility and the agricultural land, machines and farming know-how for the field trials.

The quality assurance within this part of the activities is done via IGZ - consulting, sampling, analysing, interpreting and feeding back into the composting processes.

The following **Table 4** presets the key and supplementary roles as well as the partners and alliances needed for the GE circular value chain.

Table 4: Key and supplementary roles, needed partners and alliances at the German pilot region (GE)

Key roles	Responsibilities	Resources
Sanitation service provider	Collection of human excreta	Fleet of dry toilets Back-end employees for construction of toilets Educated personnel for festival engagement
Fertiliser production facility and its manager	Production of fertiliser from human excreta compliant with quality standards	Ownership of machinery, know how, operational personnel to undertake operation and quality assurance
Location provider for recycling facilities	Provides location for infrastructure for human excreta treatment	Area, permits

Local farm	Enabling field trials for improved market offering and, in this case, also the provision of location for infrastructure for human excreta treatment	Permits, risk friendliness
Marketer	To bring produce on the market	Distribution network
Supplementary roles	Responsibilities	Resources
Technology provider	For supply of technology and equipment to operate a composting facility	Faeces treatment technology including supplementary devices for loading, unloading and cleaning of bins.
Festivals and events	For facilitation of human excreta collection and communication of circular value chain	Customers and communication channels
Retail chains	For distribution of produce to users	Trucks for transportation Farmer cooperation and advisory (for agricultural advising, and nutrient broker capabilities) Intellectual resources such as agricultural expertise and knowledge of potential nutrient input streams in the region. Fulfilment center (for packaging and/or shipping of compost) Packaging equipment and processes for shipping Garden retailers (for improved adoption and distribution) Distribution networks and provision of purchase channels for B2C segments.
Needed partners/alliances	Responsibilities	Resources
Public authorities: fertiliser/building/water/environmental authorities	To ensure the right permissions related to composting facilities, wastewater management, etc.)	Power to grant permission for operation.
National standards organisation	To enable guidance on quality assurance.	Institutional legitimacy Testing equipment

➤ **Spanish pilot region**

The implementation of circular N & P flow models necessitates strong collaboration across multiple sectors (see **Table 5**). Key actors include WWTP operators, agricultural cooperatives, technology providers, regulatory agencies, and research institutions. Establishing alliances between these stakeholders ensures the successful deployment of nutrient recovery systems. Additionally, engaging municipalities, environmental groups, and industry representatives fosters a multi-stakeholder approach that aligns with sustainability goals. Encouraging partnerships with start-ups and SMEs in the bio-based fertiliser sector can accelerate innovation and market penetration.

Table 5: Key and supplementary roles, needed partners and alliances at the Spanish pilot region

Key roles	Responsibilities	Resources
Public water authority	Provision of wastewater	Wastewater treatment plant
Technology provider	Production of reclaimed water	Production facility, irrigation tanks, and mixing units; Intellectual resources such as proprietary knowledge; Water engineers and technical experts
Technology provider	Nutrient control and decision-support	Intellectual resources such as proprietary knowledge; Developers and software engineers
Research institution	Data analysis and use-validation	Water scientists; Communication specialists
Farmer cooperative	Commercialisation of agricultural output and agronomical advising	Agricultural advisors; Distribution network; Brand equity within food industry
Supplementary roles	Responsibilities	Resources
Irrigation communities	Provision of well-water to dilute reclaimed water	Ownership of wells for dilution of reclaimed water
Regional government	Establishment of new piping infrastructure	Ownership and expansion of piping infrastructure
Food retailers	Close the nutrient loop towards end-consumers by marketing the end-product	Distribution and purchase channel
Needed partners / alliances	Responsibilities	Resources
Third-party certification bodies	Development of suitable certification for fruits grown with reclaimed water	Legitimacy and customer evaluation channel

River Bassin Authority	Efficient and smooth permissions to use reclaimed water	Permission grants for reclaimed water use
Local municipality	Brings visibility and institutional trust	Visibility and institutional trust

5.2 Market uptake

This subchapter provides strategic insights to create an enabling environment for the market uptake of the pilot region solutions (e.g., aspects to be covered, required TRL, social acceptance, potential customers, early-adopters of the innovative solutions, etc.). The different aspects covered have been elaborated in collaboration with WP3 (IRS, Triodos, TRANSITION) and WP5 (IRIDRA, CERTH).

As an example, social acceptance must be addressed, as it has proven to be a barrier across all pilot regions. The challenges relate to a lack of knowledge regarding the negative impacts of N & P, misconceptions about the removal of pollutants in WWTPs, a cultural absence of practices related to the reuse of human excreta as fertiliser, and negative perceptions concerning the quality of fertilisers derived from such human sources. To improve the willingness to adopt fertilisers based on human excreta, it is essential to focus on these issues through public awareness campaigns, farmer education, and strategic collaboration with agricultural organisations.

With regards to customer segments, there exists a wide range of potential clients, however closely connected to the unique value proposition derived from the products or services being offered. For products classified as fertilisers that can serve as substitutes for conventional ones - whether in granulated, liquid, or compost form - the most obvious customer segment is farmers. However, due to limited volumes of human excreta available as input for fertiliser production, it is often not feasible to meet the demand from this segment alone. While production is scaled up, other customer segments can contribute to ensuring the economic viability of the circular business model (elaborated below).

➤ Swedish pilot region

For the Swedish pilot region, it has been suggested that information campaigns should focus on how food is grown, emphasising that the bio-based fertilisers used for fertilisation do not end up in the final product. It is especially important to target end consumers with this message. Providing incentives can help encourage the adoption of new types of toilets as well. Additionally, highlighting the benefits of using local resources and presenting fertiliser as a recycled material can make the concept more appealing and support broader acceptance.

Potential customers:

- B2C (Business-to-Consumer): Hobby and urban gardeners who value environmentally friendly and pioneering products for use in home gardens.

- Public or private building owners (e.g., airports, highway stations, sports arenas, private households) are interested in installing decentralised human excreta collection and fertiliser production systems.
- Festivals and events, where human excreta management is required.
- Public venues, including camping sites, remote areas, and construction sites, that seek sustainable sanitation solutions.

Early adopters:

In relation to sanitation services, there is significant reliance on the willingness of event organisers to adopt sustainable sanitation solutions instead of conventional chemical toilet systems. Factors such as festival certifications play an important role in supporting this transition.

Additionally, the uptake of fertiliser products derived from human excreta relies on willingness from farmers and hobby gardeners to use these products on equal terms with conventional fertilisers. While it is most likely that highly environmentally conscious farmers and consumers will represent the early adopters, product certification is essential to assure safety and demonstrate improved environmental impact. This may facilitate broader adoption within the segment.

Certification also plays a critical role for early adopters within the food industry. It must be acknowledged that, to fully close the nutrient loop, early engagement from actors in the manufacturing industry is necessary. Concerns from potential early adopters revolve around perceived risks to brand reputation, in which certifications that communicate consumer safety and positive environmental impact are crucial in mitigating such barriers and encourage adoption within this sector.

➤ **German pilot region**

To increase a wider acceptance, a solution to the German pilot region may be to emphasise the agricultural process and the societal benefits, rather than the fertiliser or compost itself. The emphasis on the ecological benefits (save water, mitigate eutrophication) may also be a crucial element of the value proposition. Based on this, the establishment of a standard to account for "Low impact fertilisers" is in progress.

Furthermore, there is a value proposition serving the interests of the municipalities with regard to a) reducing cost of treatment, b) reducing pressure on expansion of existing WWTP and c) adding a solution for non-sewered households.

Potential customers for the technologies of VN and GE:

- B2C (Business-to-Consumer): Hobby and urban gardeners who value environmentally friendly and pioneering fertilisers or compost for use in home gardens.

- B2B (Business-to-Business): Organisations such as golf courses and professional gardening services seeking sustainable alternatives to conventional fertilisers and compost for use in their own operations.
- B2G (Business-to-Government): Local municipalities seeking locally sourced fertilisers or compost for public green spaces.
- Public or private building owners (e.g., airports, highway stations, sports arenas, private households) interested in installing decentralised urine collection and fertiliser production systems.
- Sanitation providers, farmers, or public authorities aiming to implement in-house recycling systems for urine.

Early adopters:

The adoption of innovative sanitation technologies depends heavily on the engagement of both private and public building owners. To enhance the attractiveness of installations, like the VN urine treatment systems, alignment with building certification schemes and the integration of benefits relevant to ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance) reporting may increase interest. Particularly among real estate developers, who may then view alternative approaches to traditional sewage connections as advantageous. For GE early adopters may be value driven B2C customers who are not as price sensitive as larger farmers.

➤ **Spanish pilot region**

Achieving widespread adoption of reclaimed water and bio-based fertilisers requires addressing technological readiness, social acceptance, and economic feasibility. Early adopters, such as large-scale agricultural producers and organic farming initiatives, play a pivotal role in demonstrating the effectiveness of circular solutions. Engaging supply chain actors, including distributors and retailers, is essential to expanding market reach. Economic incentives, such as subsidies or preferential regulatory treatment, can further facilitate adoption. Additionally, consumer education campaigns can help overcome public hesitancy regarding the use of reclaimed water in agriculture.

The emphasis on the similarities to free-range-eggs can be a selling point. It is not organic but more sustainable. The use of reclaimed water should also be incentivised and/or awarded. To show that reclaimed water is not waste, but a resource can also be an important aspect.

Potential customer segments:

- Public water authorities for tertiary treatment of wastewater.
- Farmer cooperatives or irrigation communities for in-house water reclamation.
- Other public or private organisations irrigating green areas (municipalities, gardening/landscaping organisations, golf courses, football fields).

Early adopters:

- Certification and eco-labeling are vital to communicate environmental value to eco-conscious end-consumers and increase adoption among these consumers, while also enabling early adopters like TROPS to gain premium payments from their sustainable farming practices.

5.3 Governance solutions

In collaboration with WP4 (ICLEI), this subchapter provides strategic insights into the implementation of governance schemes that underpin circularity of N & P flows (e.g., governance solutions included in pilot regions).

Effective governance entails developing regulatory mechanisms that incentivise nutrient recovery while maintaining environmental and public health standards. In that sense, robust governance frameworks are critical for enabling circular nutrient flows. At the same time, local and regional policies supporting the integration of bio-based fertilisers into conventional farming practices are fundamental as they can encourage uptake.

Governance models should also include financial mechanisms to support infrastructure investments and operational costs. For this, multi-level governance, incorporating municipal, regional, and national authorities, ensures comprehensive oversight and coordination.

Also, governance schemes are crucial to scale up nutrient recycling that offloads current WWTPs, especially because the EU's new Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive would otherwise force governments and municipalities to invest millions of euros on upgrading current WWTPs and/or building new ones. The collaboration across various public sectors including planning, wastewater, food and agriculture is of great importance.

Following, some general and pilot-specific potential reforms have already been detected that will be elaborated in more detail in D4.4 (Governance framework and implementation guidelines) due in M36 (November 2025).

Waste:

- Enable management outside of EU waste law (e.g., create parallel regime/specific rules for 'secondary raw materials' or similar) and/or adapt the approach of EU waste law (provide requisite flexibility).
- Clarify EU waste law to confirm flexibility as to applicable waste regime and how to implement the UWWTD.
- Develop/mandate the creation of relevant EU end-of-waste criteria.

Water reuse:

- Mandate the implementation of the water reuse regulation across the EU (no opt-outs provided – EU law provides sufficient flexibility to address issues if, for instance, nitrate vulnerable zones).
- Confirm that reclaimed water is no longer waste (waiting for an answer by DG ENV).

Fertilisers:

- Amend the FPR to add further CMCs/adapt existing CMCs
- Advocate for national fertiliser legislation to permit expressly the use of human excreta as an input.

Organics:

- Faeces/urine/derived fertilisers not seemingly permitted (reclaimed water, yes).

Others:

- Update Environmental Quality Standards Directive (EQSD), Sewage Sludge Directive, etc.

➤ **Swedish pilot region**

Governance Solutions in Place or in Progress

Sweden benefits from a strong legal foundation for circularity through its Environmental Code (Miljöbalken), which requires responsible use and recycling of natural resources (§1, Chapter 1). This broad mandate supports nutrient recovery initiatives, even though excreta reuse is not yet explicitly regulated, it can be legally used as fertiliser already.

Further Potential Solutions

The Swedish pilot builds on this foundation through two strategic initiatives:

The development of a Low-Environmental-Impact Fertiliser (LEIF) Label (to be launched EU wide), designed to inform and incentivise the use of fertilisers with minimal environmental footprints, such as urine-derived products.

The Circular Nutrient Fertiliser (CNF) Standard (Swedish level), aimed at defining quality and safety criteria for bio-based fertilisers to support broader market uptake.

At the local level, cooperation with municipalities and wastewater utilities in regions like Gotland and Uppsala has the potential to scale-up source-separation strategies to reduce pressure on wastewater treatment systems, especially in areas with high seasonal tourism. Pilot actors such as S360 are also in the process of obtaining environmental permits for urine treatment facilities, navigating classification challenges where urine is still often considered "waste" under existing law.

Despite progress, several governance challenges remain. A more coherent regulatory framework is needed to support the classification and use of source-separated human excreta as a resource, particularly in decentralised settings. Future governance efforts could include:

Collaborating with wastewater utilities to manage seasonal capacity issues in tourist-heavy regions, where traditional WWTPs often exceed capacity, leading to untreated discharges.

Targeted support for rural areas, where centralised treatment investments are limited, making decentralised nutrient recovery systems a more viable option.

Improved inter-sectoral coordination between sanitation, agriculture, food, and environmental departments to support nutrient recycling from source to soil.

➤ **German pilot region**

- Governance solutions in place or in progress:
 - Certification of urine-based fertiliser in single member countries instead of at EU level, then mutual recognition by other countries.
 - Participation to the German regulatory sandboxes network contributed largely to the expert consultation for the proposed legislation of the Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Action on 'Regulatory Sandboxes'.
- Further potential solutions:
 - Potential for ROS to alleviate existing wastewater treatment capacity issues related to temporary nutrients peaks during festivals by offering a separate decentralised collection method.
 - DIN SPEC 91421 giving technical guidance on the quality assurance of bio-fertilisers made from human excreta.

➤ **Spanish pilot region**

In the Spanish pilot region, several governance solutions have been identified, either in place or under development:

- Use of regional funds to invest in wastewater reuse, accessed through enacted drought legislation.
- Collaboration with Farmers Association TROPS to pilot growing mangos and avocados.

Further potential solutions:

- Partner with public authorities about increasing resilience: wastewater reclamation for fertigation of land can provide essential irrigation in high-risk drought regions - freshwater needs are reduced, as well as local synthetic fertiliser demand.

5.4 Adequate incentives

In collaboration with WP3 (TRANSITION, Triodos, HCU, IRS) and WP4 (ICLEI) this subchapter provides examples of incentives to implement the circular models in the pilot regions (e.g., financial incentives, certifications, subsidies, etc.).

➤ **Swedish pilot region**

- Internalisation of external costs by public authorities plays a key role in highlighting the economic burdens associated with pollutant removal and the environmental costs of pollution, costs that are often borne by society but not formally recognised in market prices. By accounting for these externalities, the solutions proposed in the pilot regions can emerge as competitive alternatives, and in some cases, even more cost-effective than conventional wastewater treatment systems.
- Examples for external costs that can be prevented with the pilot solutions are: the environmental damage of N & P in water bodies and ground water; the cost for upgrading WWTPs with N & P removal processes; the cost for connecting remote settlements, public toilets, tourist infrastructure buildings to the sewage system. Further incentives could come from the Climate Action Plans for the pilot region that suggest subsidies regarding sustainable fertiliser use and farming.
- Fertiliser certifications that guarantee the safety of bio-based fertiliser products.
- End-product certifications that assure consumers of product safety and reduced environmental impact.
- Festival and event certifications for acknowledgement of sustainable sanitation solutions.
- Direct price subsidies for bio-based fertilisers supported by the rationale that conventional fertilisers, against which bio-based products must compete, are often subsidized.
- Carbon or nitrogen credit schemes to capture environmental value generated from circular value chain.

➤ **German pilot region**

- As in the Swedish pilot region, the internalisation of external costs by public authorities plays a key role in highlighting the economic burdens associated with pollutant removal and the environmental costs of pollution, costs that are often borne by society but not formally recognised in market prices. By accounting for these externalities, the solutions proposed in the pilot regions can emerge as competitive

alternatives, and in some cases, even more cost-effective than conventional wastewater treatment systems.

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- Tariff structures can serve as instruments to raise awareness about the negative externalities associated with wastewater, and drive adoption of alternative wastewater systems.
- Building certifications that acknowledge the use of decentralised treatment systems for human excreta.
- Fertiliser certifications that guarantee the safety of bio-based fertiliser products.
- Direct price subsidies for bio-based fertilisers supported by the rationale that conventional fertilisers, against which bio-based products must compete, are often subsidised.
- Integrated public utility payments to capture societal cost savings by reducing the need for pollutant removal in WWTPs and by mitigating the externalities associated with environmental pollution.
- Governmental economic support essential to achieve price competitiveness, through mechanisms such as subsidies, CO₂ emission taxation, and compensation for avoided treatment costs.
- Investments in infrastructure are needed to enable and scale decentralised sanitation solutions.
- EU-funded R&D initiatives, such as the P2Green project, provide crucial support for innovation and development in the sector ensuring high quality outcomes.

➤ **Spanish pilot region**

- Wastewater reuse is not economically attractive given farmers have access to a well/groundwater use at a low cost despite being in a drought-prone mediterranean region. An appropriate water tariff structure could be introduced to create incentives and finance associated with water reuse costs considering these aspects:
 - polluter pays principle.
 - cover the pure and hard costs (treatment, transportation, storage).
 - fixed costs, variable costs, and seasonal costs.

- principle of cost recovery, but also principle of equity – for farmers not producing high-cost crops to avoid only high-water intensity crops dominating the region.
 - reward sustainable farming practices (e.g. reduced use of fertilisers, smaller water footprint).
 - make sure not to promote water overuse.
- Revisions to water tariff frameworks represent a critical factor in strengthening financial incentives for adopting circular models. In the case of reclaimed water, there is direct competition with well water, which is often underpriced despite being a scarce resource. Adjusting water prices to better reflect the scarcity and environmental value of water resources can enhance incentives to shift toward reclaimed alternatives.
 - End-product certifications that assure consumers of product safety and reduced environmental impact.

5.5 Policy and regulatory reforms

This subchapter provides insights into potential policy and regulatory reforms, currently being identified, to enable and implement circular models in the pilot regions. The content has been elaborated in collaboration with WP3 partners (SUSTCHEM, NUIM UCD, NUID).

This analysis is performed in detail within the D3.8 (Final report describing the status of the legislative framework, future perspectives, and recommendations both in pilots and followers).

In general, some issues that have become apparent include: the lack of clarity within the waste regime (e.g. regarding the applicability of the Urban WasteWater Treatment Directive) and concerns regarding implementation of Article 6 of the Waste Framework Directive (end-of-waste criteria); the insufficiency of the Fertilising Products Regulation to encompass P2Green products; and the inflexibility of the EU's laws on organic farming. These issues are within the EU law but highlighted and exemplified within the regions.

D3.8 will include recommendations regarding policy areas and specific laws for review and potential legislative reforms, especially at the EU level. For instance, this could include recommendations to develop one or more Component Material Categories to encompass human excreta under the EU's Fertilising Products Regulation, to clarify and update elements in the EU waste legislation, and to develop relevant EU-level end-of-waste criteria and/or further obligations to develop criteria. EU-wide reforms would be most advantageous for the main part, but national or regional reforms may be considered too. These recommendations regarding potential reforms are informed by

the legal research alongside the practical experiences of the pilot regions (and the follower regions).

In this respect, it is useful to highlight some legal issues that the pilots have encountered that they consider meriting reform or at least review and potentially clarification from their perspectives. These will then be considered during the development of the legislative report (D3.8).

➤ **Swedish pilot region**

- Of particular significance so far for the Swedish pilot region is the use of urine on organic certified farms. This was accepted to pre-joining the EU in 1994. The use of urine-based fertilisers needs to be re-evaluated.

➤ **German pilot region**

- Issues arise regarding waste law and the lack of clarity stemming from the EU's UWWTD.
- Enabling treatment of human excreta as waste and providing guidance on treatment and quality assurance.
- Adding non-sewered sanitation solutions to the options mentioned in UWWTD for the provision of sanitation service for small communities (i.e. < 10.000 p.e.).
- Subsidies for zero emission or low impact solutions.

➤ **Spanish pilot region**

- Issues arise regarding the complexity of the Water Reuse Regulation and also the law on organic farming. It remains to be seen whether reforms are needed/merited, or instead whether simply clarifications by the relevant authorities would suffice.

5.6 Capacity building and training needs

This subchapter provides insights into the required skills, expertise, resources, training, etc. identified so as to enable and implement circular models in the pilot regions. The content of these sections has been elaborated in collaboration with WP3 (SUSTCHEM, NUIM UCD, NUID) and WP4 (CBS).

In light of how complex, and frequently unclear and confusing, the law is for the relevant authorities, certification bodies, stakeholders etc and the need for the public authorities to be able to engage (e.g. provide authorisations or clear answers), EU and national guidance documents would be useful, but also perhaps information or training sessions as to what is required and what is permitted or feasible.

If the law is reformed, this will become increasingly necessary as, even if the law is clarified, it may become more complex and less familiar.

While local authorities are frequently knowledgeable about their own local regimes, they may not consider or know and understand the applicable EU law which underpins the local regimes.

➤ **Swedish pilot region**

Currently, there is a lack of clearly defined stakeholders and responsibilities for the collection, treatment, and distribution of urine in the Swedish context. Strengthening institutional capacity requires clarifying roles, improving coordination among actors, and developing regulatory frameworks to support safe and efficient resource recovery and reuse. For urine treatment facilities, having a specialist trained on site is crucial to ensure safe and effective processing. This includes managing the handling and storage of source-separated urine, operating relevant treatment technologies, and overseeing safety protocols. The specialist is also responsible for monitoring treatment parameters, maintaining hygiene standards, and ensuring the infrastructure functions reliably to produce a safe, high-quality end product.

Additionally, policy and economic barriers that hinder the adoption of resource recovery must be addressed in the Swedish pilot. A major challenge is the lack of clear regulations and institutional frameworks, which create uncertainty around responsibilities and compliance. Additionally, the absence of incentives or subsidies limits the motivation for stakeholders to invest in and adopt these systems. Strengthening capacity in this area involves developing enabling policies, establishing supportive governance structures, and creating financial mechanisms that encourage sustainable implementation.

➤ **German pilot region**

The successful implementation and operation of the nutrient recycling systems in the German pilot region require targeted capacity building and well-defined roles for operational personnel.

For the composting facility, the presence of a trained specialist is essential to ensure the safe and efficient handling of raw materials derived from dry toilets, as well as the operation of heavy machinery such as a wheel loader. This role involves overseeing the hygienisation process, maintaining quality control parameters, and managing the composting infrastructure. The role demands both technical expertise and practical experience, and appropriate training programs should be made available to develop and maintain this skillset locally.

In parallel, the urine treatment system, which uses specialised technology provided by VN, requires a different operational setup. A maintenance contract with the technology supplier ensures remote monitoring and technical oversight of the system. This arrangement significantly reduces the need for extensive technical expertise on-site. Instead, local operators require only basic mechanical troubleshooting skills to handle minor issues and maintain day-to-day operations. These skills are to be delivered

through dedicated training sessions facilitated by VN, ensuring that personnel are equipped to support the system's functionality while relying on the supplier for more complex technical support.

Together, these measures underline the importance of early-stage training and the development of local operational competencies to secure the long-term sustainability and scalability of the pilot systems.

➤ **Spanish pilot region**

Training should cover both the technical operation of water reclamation facilities and the implementation of the Risk Management Plan (RMP), as required by Regulation (EU) 2020/741 on water reuse. Operators must understand not only system functionality but also risk mitigation measures to ensure health and environmental safety and adhere to the drafted RMP.

Additionally, to effectively utilise reclaimed water in the Spanish pilot region, capacity building must address several technical and operational challenges. Key areas include enhancing skills in calculating precise irrigation and nutrient dosing, implementing “water on demand” systems, and using real-time sensor data for informed decision-making. Building capacity also involves scaling up and adapting treatment technologies and infrastructure to improve the accessibility and consistent quality of reclaimed water. Furthermore, technical training is needed to assess the nutrient composition of reclaimed water, mitigate its potential impacts on soil health, and accurately estimate crop water requirements under reclaimed water use.

As part of local capacity building, workshops and technical training sessions by experts can be conducted to highlight the pilot site and provide hands-on demonstrations of digital aggregation tools and their application. These sessions can enhance stakeholders understanding, promote practical learning, and build technical skills for the effective application of digital solutions in the wastewater sector. Showcasing technologies and results from the test site to local authorities is essential for demonstrating proof of concept and building the foundation for wider adoption and future implementation.

5.7 Technologies implemented

A concise overview of the technology systems underpinning the circular value chains in the pilot regions is provided below to support the understanding of their structure and functioning. Detailed technical specifications, process configurations and operational parameters are described in Deliverable 1.6 - Progress in set up of pilot regions⁸ and are therefore not repeated here.

⁸ Beneker, González, Parfitt, Senecal, D1.6 rev1, Progress in set up of pilot regions, 2024, P2Green consortium. Available at: <https://p2green.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/03/Set-up-operation-and-validation-of-Pilot-Regions-1.pdf>

➤ **Swedish pilot region**

The Swedish pilot region is based on source separation of urine and its transformation into both a liquid fertilizer and a solid granular fertiliser, enabling the recovery and reuse of nutrients within a decentralised system configuration.

Within this circular value chain, urine is collected through urine-diverting sanitation systems, including both fixed installations, such as urine diverting toilets, and mobile units such as urinals, that are deployed at public events. The collected urine is subsequently processed using a stabilisation and drying technology system, which reduces water content and concentrates nutrients.

The treatment process results in a granular, circular fertiliser product, characterised by improved handling properties, reduced transport volume and compatibility with conventional agricultural equipment. The technology system, developed by SLU and S360, is being further optimised towards modular and scalable configurations, including off-grid operation. S360 have also seen an increase in demand for liquid fertilizer and are therefore testing the concentrated liquid urine in projects with Swedish municipalities.

The recovered nutrient product can be applied in agricultural production systems, particularly in cereal cultivation, thereby closing the loop between urban sanitation systems and agricultural nutrient demand.

This circular value chain is characterised by the decentralised capture of nutrient flows through source separation, physicochemical treatment for nutrient stabilisation and concentration, with a focus on reintegrating nutrients into agricultural production with urine-based fertiliser products.

➤ **German pilot region (KWB & VN)**

The KWB and VunaNexus pathway focuses on the centralised processing of source-separated urine into a standardised liquid bio-based fertiliser product, supporting the recovery of nutrient flows at regional scale.

Within this value chain, urine is collected from decentralised urine-diverting sanitation systems, including public sanitation infrastructure and event-based collection schemes, and transported to a central treatment facility at KWB.

The core technology system is the VunaNexus urine treatment system. It integrates stabilisation, filtration and distillation processes to recover nutrients, remove all micropollutants and pathogens, and produce the certified liquid fertiliser product Aurin®. The system ensures product standardisation, hygienisation and compliance with regulatory requirements.

The treatment installation is being implemented in Eberswalde, building on existing infrastructure to facilitate integration into regional waste and resource management systems. The resulting fertiliser product is applied in agricultural field trials to assess agronomic performance and operational feasibility.

This circular value chain is characterised by centralised processing of collected urine streams, production of regulated mineral bio-based fertiliser products, and integration into conventional agricultural fertilisation practices.

➤ **German pilot region (GE)**

The second German value chain focuses on the recovery of nutrients and organic matter from solid human excreta through biological treatment processes, following decentralised collection.

Within this circular value chain, dry sanitation systems are deployed in decentralised and temporary contexts (e.g. festivals, public spaces and off-grid locations), enabling the separate collection of faecal material.

The collected material is treated using a thermophilic composting technology system in container-based installations, ensuring hygienisation, stabilisation of organic matter and reduction of volume. The process results in a compost-based bio-based fertiliser product (KIT), characterised by its organic carbon content and soil-conditioning properties.

The treatment installations are located at the Vagtshoff site, where the compost is further matured and applied in agricultural production systems, contributing to both nutrient supply and soil quality improvement.

This value chain is characterised by decentralised collection of solid excreta, biological treatment via controlled thermophilic composting, and production of organic bio-based fertiliser products supporting soil fertility.

➤ **Spanish pilot region**

The Spanish pilot region is based on the reclamation of treated municipal wastewater and reuse for agricultural fertigation, representing a water-based approach to nutrient recovery.

Within this circular value chain, municipal wastewater is treated in a conventional WWTP and subsequently processed through a water reclamation system, including advanced filtration and disinfection processes.

Reclaimed water, containing nutrients, is used for irrigation of high-value crops (e.g. avocado and mango), enabling the simultaneous recovery of water and nutrient flows. The system incorporates continuous monitoring of physicochemical parameters and integrated in a Smart Fertigation Tool which supports the optimisation of nutrient dosing according to crop requirements.

This approach combines advanced wastewater treatment and reuse, recovery of nutrient flows embedded in irrigation practices, and digital optimisation of fertigation strategies. This circular value reduces freshwater abstraction and enhances nutrient use efficiency in water-scarce regions.

5.8 Operational aspects

This subchapter highlights other relevant operational aspects to be considered for each of the pilot regions, such as logistics for collection and transport of human excreta, collection and storage of produced biofertilisers, hardware and software requirements, etc.

➤ Swedish pilot region

Collection and Transport of Urine

- TD dispatches urinals and soon Kissamajas already loaded with the stabiliser (provided by S360) to ensure odour management and the retention of N in the urine.
- S360 ensures hygienic collection, storage, and transport of urine through sealed, airtight, and standardised containers (IBCs).
- Urine is pumped into one-cubic-meter tanks (IBC) at the collection site by S360 and sealed upon reaching capacity. Sealed storage prevents emissions and odor while preserving nutrients until processing. Personnel wear respiratory masks, gloves and protective glasses.

Storage and Logistics

- The IBCs are transported to either TD or S360 site and stored sealed until processed. Transport of full bins is done by an external logistics company. Tools, pumps, and measuring equipment are stored in weatherproof facilities at S360 premises.

Hardware and Software

- Manual temperature and pH measurement tools are used to monitor the urine during storage and processing (drying).

Freshwater and Wastewater Management

- No direct water supply or sewage connections are available at the storage or processing site. Fresh water is supplied in 25 L containers to be used if an emergency. Otherwise, there is tapped water available inside the facilities rented by TB and the property owner of S360.

Operational costs

- Ongoing costs include electricity and additives like compost. The processing facility requires a part-time person with no background experience needed.

➤ German pilot region

Collection and Storage of Human Excreta

- GE ensures hygienic collection, storage, and transport of faeces (until hygienisation) through sealed, airtight, and standardised containers.
- Urine is pumped into one-cubic-meter tanks at the collection site by subcontractor Finizio GmbH and sealed upon reaching capacity. Sealed storage prevents emissions and odor while preserving nutrients until processing.

Human Excreta Handling

- Solid contents from dry toilets (excreta, chopped straw and toilet paper) are collected in mobile solid waste containers (FSB) with 180 liters volume. After transportation to the recycling plant, the FSB are emptied into the hygienisation container using a hydraulic lifting and tipping system without direct contact.
- Urine tanks can be stored without shelf-time-limitation when sealed and contents can be pumped to urine treatment facility on demand.
- FSBs are cleaned at a mobile washing station, with wastewater collected in a retention basin.

Human Excreta Processing

- The hygienisation container takes in approx. 16 tonnes of fresh dry toilet contents. After thermal treatment and drainage, this mass is reduced to approx. 11 tonnes, and for further treatment in the composting container, about 12 meters of length and storage capacity for approx. 22 tonnes of compost are required.
- The nitrification rate of the urine treatment plant ranges from 50 – 30 0mg N·L⁻¹·d⁻¹ depending on the type of urine and treatment context (e.g. temperature). In this case, the latest lab results show a concentration of 1500-2500 mg Nsol/L in stored percurine and a higher amount in organics than what would come from flush toilets or urinals in a building. This results in stronger competition between the different types of bacteria in the system, leading to much longer hydraulic retention times than expected of at least 10 days and a reactor size >7 times higher than the expected treatment capacity.

Safety Guidelines

- Protective measures for employees include technical, organisational, and personal safety regulations.
- Personnel must wear waterproof full protective suits and respiratory masks / facemasks, when handling fresh dry toilet contents. After hygienisation of the material it is required to wear protective workwear.
- Work clothing should remain in a designated decontamination area, with showers and lockers provided.
- Annual inspection of all machinery and mobile electrical equipment is mandatory.

- ABC fire extinguishers are required near all electrical installations.

Storage and Logistics

- Seasonal dry toilet operations demand increased storage capacity.
- GE's festival toilets require 200 m² storage area per 72 units.
- Transport choices for toilet infrastructure (toilets, empty FSBs) depend on quantity, distance and availability of in-house drivers and vehicles:
 - o Option 1: 3.5t van with a 3.5t trailer, transporting 12 toilets all inclusive.
 - o Option 2: for larger distances usually the trailers with 12 toilets are transported "pickaback" by an external logistics company.
- Transport of full FSBs is done by an external logistics company.
- The GE urine IBCs are emptied on the festivals by external sanitation service providers and then loaded onto the trailers. Urine is not yet part of the circular GE sanitation system.
- Tools, pumps, and measuring equipment should be stored in weatherproof facilities.

Hardware and Software

- The hygienisation of the biomass is achieved through thermal treatment resulting from biological activity induced by active aeration in commercially available, insulated roll-off containers (30 m³ filling volume) in accordance with DIN 30722. The containers comply with the requirements of the German BioWaste Ordinance (BioAbfV) and are transported using hook-lift trucks. A membrane roof cover allows for odour-free gas exchange without ammonia loss.
- The following composting step takes place in an EarthFlow® composting container, where the biomass is actively aerated and mixed by an automatic mixing device.
- The urine processing plant may release minimal foam, which is handled via underground piping.
- Distilled water from the evaporation process could be reused as process water.

Operational costs

- Ongoing costs include additives like green waste, biochar and clay minerals (bentonite).
- Wastewater disposal by a pump truck service varies in cost based on volumes.
- The composting process consumes ~7 kWh electricity and 13 l diesel per t of output material, with maintenance costs estimated at ~1% of construction costs.

- The primary operating cost for urine treatment is electricity consumption for the evaporation process, estimated at ~95 kWh per cubic meter of processed urine.
- The composting facility requires a trained specialist full-time for the season from April to November (approx. 8 months = 125 days = 1,000 hours per year).
- For the operations of the urine treatment, a maintenance contract with the technology supplier VN is required, including remote control of the system. Local Operators need only basic mechanical troubleshooting skills, provided through training by VN, and approx. 1-2 hours per week.
- For the collection and logistics of urine and Aurin, subcontractors have been contracted at a cost of 3,000 € per year but this is hoped to develop into a service fee income for KWB rather than an expense.

➤ **Spanish pilot region**

Collection and Treatment of Municipal Wastewater

- The WRP receives secondary-treated effluent from the municipal WWTP and processes it through three main stages: disc filtration (through 100 µm disc filters to remove suspended solids), ozone disinfection (primary disinfection), and hydrogen peroxide (residual disinfection). It is semi-automated and includes pressure sensors and cleaning alarms.
- This produces reclaimed water compliant with EU and Spanish regulations (Regulation EU 2020/741 and Royal Decree 1085/2024). The WRP has a nominal daily treatment capacity of 16 m³, working 5.5 hours/day.
- Reclaimed water produced is compliant with EU and Spanish regulations (Regulation EU 2020/741 and Royal Decree 1085/2024).

Storage of Reclaimed Water

- Reclaimed water is pumped to a mixing station with a measurement tank permanently filled with reclaimed water, where sensors connected to a Hach SC-1000 data logger continuously monitor water quality parameters.
- Reclaimed water is conveyed by gravity to a 7,000 L storage tank for irrigation use.
- Separate pipelines ensure no cross-contamination with the freshwater network.

Freshwater and Solid Waste Management

- Freshwater (well water) is stored in a 7,000 L storage tank for irrigation use (control treatment using local water and mineral fertilisation).
- Solid waste produced during wastewater filtration process is collected and managed by the WWTP utility.

Irrigation and Fertilisation Operations

- Reclaimed water reaches the field trials via buried piping.
- A fertigation cabinet with injection pumps manages two tanks of fertilisers (tailored for mango and avocado). The system can apply either 100% reclaimed water, local well water, and a programmable mixture (T3), which is the preferred option due to salinity concerns.
- Fertiliser doses are currently semi-automatic and based on input from the Smart Fertigation Tool (SFT), which provides real-time data on: soil moisture (20, 60, 90 cm), electrical conductivity and temperature, reclaimed water nutrient content (N, P, K).
- The decision-making algorithm (developed by Agualytics) allows users to set irrigation windows and thresholds for each crop. Full automation is the next operational goal.

Automation and Monitoring

The system is semi-automated at present:

- Sensors provide real-time monitoring of key water quality indicators (such as turbidity, pH, temperature, electrical conductivity, and nutrient concentrations)
- The data logger records and stores measurements.
- The operation of pumps, disinfectant dosing, and irrigation cycles are programmed and controlled remotely.
- Tools and monitoring equipment are stored in a dedicated, weatherproof station adjacent to the field trials.

Maintenance activities:

- Verification of pumps and dosing equipment, visual inspection of pipelines and connections, inspecting the data logger for abnormal values.
- Control of disinfectant levels (hydrogen peroxide).
- Monitoring tank levels and filling as needed.
- Cleaning the intake filter of the reclaimed water pump.
- Automatic cleaning of disc filters with compressed air.
- Visual inspection of pipelines and connections.

Sampling and Quality Control

- Reclaimed water samples are taken regularly for quality assurance: weekly (biological parameters, such as E. coli, Legionella), biweekly or monthly (physicochemical parameters, such as nitrates, P, heavy metals, pH, DBO₅, DQO).
- Samples are analysed by certified external laboratories to ensure reclaimed water is compliant with EU and Spanish regulations (Regulation EU 2020/741 and Royal Decree 1085/2024).

Storage and Logistics

- Treated water is stored in 7,000 L tanks dedicated to reclaimed, well, and mixed water.
- Separate pipelines ensure no cross-contamination with the groundwater network.
- Tools and monitoring equipment are housed in a dedicated, weatherproof station adjacent to the test field.

Hardware and Software

- Filtration process is carried out with industrial disc filters (pore size: 100µm).
- Disinfection uses ozone injection and hydrogen peroxide dosing.
- Sensors are connected to a Hach SC-1000 logger for centralised data acquisition.
- Smart fertigation tool under development will allow remote control and adjustment of irrigation and fertigation routines.

Operational Costs

- Regular costs include hydrogen peroxide, electricity, and eventual replacement of filters or sensor components.
- Labour requirements consist of supervision and technical maintenance, which can be conducted by trained personnel without specialised background.
- The Smart Fertigation Tool is expected to reduce nutrient losses and improve resource efficiency, minimising overall input costs (i.e., mineral fertilisers).

5.9 Potential for replication

In collaboration with WP5 (CERTH, IRIDRA) this subchapter describes the potential for replication of the circular models. Rather than dividing the subchapter into pilot regions, it has been divided by topic identified for replication, keeping in bracket the pilot region providing the solution.

Portable toilets/urinals (Sweden, Germany)

The Swedish/German pilot technologies have some potential for replication in the follower regions to replace conventional portable toilets used in construction sites,

events, festivals, etc. under certain circumstances. The logistics of having two types of portable toilets (standard and urinal/urine separating toilet) will be more complex. In major events the total number of portable toilets (standard and urinals) will probably remain the same or slightly increase compared to the current situation of just standard type portable toilets. However, in small construction sites that currently employ just one standard type of portable toilet, adding a urinal will dramatically increase the cost, given the fact that the transportation to/from the customer's site represents most of the rental cost.

More challenges appear once we move further down the logistics chain. The second highest cost is the one associated with emptying/cleaning the toilets, which will not vary significantly between standard and urinal types of toilets. However, the cost of disposing wastewater is negligible since WWTPs that receive it measure the influent quantity rather than quality. It is evident that under the current legislative framework, such a company does not have any economic benefit to change the way of doing business. Let alone the sizeable upfront investment in expanding its facilities, purchasing new equipment, higher operational costs, retraining staff etc.

Additionally, these entities are usually located around large city centers with minimal interaction with rural agricultural regions. On top of that, agricultural businesses in some follower regions (e.g., Greece) are typically small family-owned enterprises that cover their needs in agricultural supplies (e.g., fertilisers) from resellers close to their headquarters. Therefore, it is very difficult to penetrate the market and sell bio-fertiliser through the usual channels.

Urine diverting toilets (Sweden)

The potential for replication of urine diverting toilets is even lower compared to portable toilets due to the fact that the majority of the population resides in multistory buildings in city centers. For instance, most of the current building stock in Greece was built from the 1960s until the 1980s with little or none shared and backup areas able to host storing and/or separating equipment. Therefore, such an installation is only possible technically and financially in new buildings. However, increasing the complexity of sewage pipping will eventually raise the building costs. Therefore, it can only be enforced through relevant legislation to reduce the waste streams of residential buildings.

Recovery of nutrients from urine (Sweden, Germany)

The recovery of nutrients from urine has shown potential for replication particularly among farming cooperatives and large buildings, both public and private. Farming cooperatives are interested in the opportunity to produce fertilisers for use in their fields, while other stakeholders see either a potential economic return (in the case of private entities) or a chance to promote circularity and foster new research opportunities (in the case of public institutions). Within the P2Green project, three stakeholders have been

identified within the following regions as interested in adopting urine-based fertiliser recovery technologies:

- Finagricola (Italy), an agricultural cooperative;
- Chef Express (Italy), a highway station operator;
- Agronomy University of Athens (Greece).

Compost production from faeces (Germany)

As for the potential replication of faeces recovery technologies for compost production, the main interested stakeholders are portable toilet operators, who are attracted by the marketing opportunities and potential for profit. Within the P2Green project, two such operators have been identified within the following regions:

- Geon WC (Greece);
- Rolling Hygienic (Hungary).

Treated wastewater reuse (Spain)

The possibility of using treated wastewater for irrigation has attracted interest from farming cooperatives, who are keen on using fertigation in their fields, as well as from municipalities and irrigation associations, since the reuse of wastewater contributes to reducing the depletion of water resources and reduction of fertiliser use. Within the P2Green project, two stakeholders have shown interest in replicating the pilot technology within the following regions:

- TOEV (Greece), an association for irrigation;
- Finagricola (Italy), an agricultural cooperative.

The Spanish pilot technology has the biggest potential for replication in one of the following regions (i.e., Greece) contrary to source separation. Over 260 wastewater WWTPs are currently in operation in Greece, a lot of which are located near agricultural areas making it easier to fertilise using the nutrient-rich effluent. In some cases, the treated effluent is discharged into the water body and a few kilometers downstream pumped up for irrigation by farmers. Therefore, the Spanish pilot technology will eliminate this loop, save energy and help preserve the water bodies. At the same time, this technology will boost the rates of wastewater recycling and will help tackle the water scarcity problem affecting South Europe. Despite not affecting directly people's routine, concrete legislation is required to increase water recycling and pave the way for investments around nutrient recovery.

5.10 Quality assurance

This subchapter covers quality assurance, a crucial aspect in the production of recycling fertilisers, especially when derived from human excreta. Ensuring that these products are effective and free from harmful heavy metals, organic pollutants, pharmaceutical

residues, and pathogens is essential for protecting both human health and the environment, as well as for gaining acceptance among farmers and consumers.

Compared to other sources of heavy metals, those found in human excreta typically contribute less than one-tenth of the total load in wastewater (Tervehauta et al., 2014). Faeces contain a higher concentration of heavy metals compared to urine (Tervehauta et al., 2014, Jönsson et al., 1997). Jönsson (2011) suggests that the fertiliser product produced from human urine can contain less heavy metals than mineral fertilisers. Heavy metal concentrations found in human urine are far below the Swedish limit for land application (Jönsson et al., 1997) and well below the levels in other biologically derived fertilisers (Hammer & Clemens, 2007; Jönsson et al., 2004). Initial analyses showed that our fertiliser had heavy metal levels below the European Union limits for fertiliser use (data not published).

Some organic micropollutants (OMP), reflecting the chemicals society uses, are primarily excreted via urine, while others are mostly excreted through faeces (Lienert et al., 2007).

In the circular utilisation of human excreta, the human and environmental risk from pharmaceutical residues is frequently discussed. They are already a problem with lack of adequate sanitation and with conventional WWTPs. Pharmaceutical residues can occur in very small quantities in wastewater, and they are difficult to detect and remove at WWTPs (Luo et al., 2014), which are usually designed to treat bulk substances (Larsen et al., 2004). After passing through the WWTP, pharmaceutical residues remain biochemically active in water and can alter the behaviour of aquatic animals (Van Donk et al., 2016; Brodin et al., 2013).

Lienert et al. (2007) analysed the excretion pathways of 212 pharmaceutical substances and found that, on average, about two-thirds of each substance is excreted through urine. Thus, removing the urine and faeces from the wastewater stream and utilising it as fertiliser could have three potential benefits. First, some degradation could occur in the field due to exposure to ultraviolet light from the sun (Kim et al., 2009). Second, microbiological activity in the soil will probably lead to degradation of pharmaceutical active ingredients (Salvia et al., 2014; Yu et al., 2013). Many hormonal pharmaceuticals are similar to naturally occurring substances for which degradation routes exist in nature (Jönsson et al., 2004). Third, households utilising specifically hazardous compounds (such as X-ray medium) could probably more easily use a special excreta management plan. If pharmaceuticals are applied to land (via re-use of excreta as a fertiliser), then we would ingest fewer compounds, compared to what we ingest via the drinking water today. A simulation study in Levén et al. (2016) found that one would have to eat carrots or potatoes every single day for over 5,000 years to get one dose of the most resilient pharmaceutical compounds (over 20,000 years for the less resilient substances). The same simulation study found that intake of pharmaceutical residues would be at least 10-fold higher through drinking tap water in Stockholm (Levén et al., 2016). According to Vinnerås et al. (2008), several pharmaceutical substances are found in higher

concentrations in animal manure compared to what can be expected in human urine. Overall, residual pharmaceuticals remaining in the fertiliser derived from human excreta are too low of a concentration to be of a risk to humans. Saying that, there is still an uncertainty about the risk of pharmaceuticals to the micro-biome of the soil.

Minimising pathogens for hygienic handling of recycling fertilisers from human excreta is a significant requirement for safe use of products derived from it. Approx. 50 % of our faeces are enterobacteria and reflect what we eat. They potentially contain harmful microorganisms such as parasites (e.g. Ascaris), bacteria (e.g. Salmonella), Viruses (e.g., COVID) of sick people, whilst urine carries no to small shares of pathogens. Prions are not excreted by humans.

The chance in source separation, which is applied in the Swedish and the German pilot regions, is founded in the fact, that harmful substances are neither diluted with water nor mixed with other sources of harmful substances. The daily per capita excretion rate of 0.15 L faeces 1.5 L urine is typically diluted with 150 L of domestic wastewater and additional rain-water run-off, resulting in a dilution factor of approx. 200 and the addition of substances from industrial wastewater, hospitals, roads among others. Separately sourced faeces and urine can be processed in a way where remaining harmful substances such as pathogens and pharmaceuticals can be removed in a targeted manner, treating significantly smaller volumes.

➤ **Swedish pilot region**

At SLU, several (other funded) projects investigating the removal of micro-pollutants during the drying process are carried out to determine that the cleanest fertiliser possible can be produced. The experiments are currently at bench-scale; however, existing technologies are being used, and adapted to urine, with the intention to be able to integrate the process before the end of this P2Green project. One study that evaluated the inactivation of 75 pharmaceuticals in urine showed that 90% of them were possible to reduce by 55% using UV light in the urine pre-drying (Demissie, 2023).

➤ **German pilot region**

IGZ responsible for analysis of the field trials apply the DIN SPEC 91421:2020 standard to assess the content of nutrients, heavy metals, organic pollutants, hygiene parameters, and pharmaceuticals in recycling fertilisers. Preliminary results show an effective removal during the recycling process (cf. D2.5 - Report on the methods used to determine agroecological impacts, due in M30).

The effective removal of pharmaceuticals from urine through the activated carbon adsorption used in the Vuna process is evidenced for 12 key parameters and requires 60 times less activated carbon than WWTPs for the removal of these substances (Köpping et al., 2020).

➤ **Spanish pilot region**

After passing through the WWTP, pharmaceutical residues remain biochemically active in water and can alter the behaviour of aquatic animals (Van Donk et al., 2016; Brodin et al., 2013). Based on this risk, with the updated UWWTD, member states are obliged to successively upgrade WWTPs with elimination technologies (typically activated carbon filtration and/or ultraviolet light) until 2045.

The raw wastewater of Algarrobo and nearby municipalities is sourced exclusively from urban settlements, with no industrial wastewater discharged into the sewage system. After the secondary treatment, the outflow is discharged entirely into the sea through an underwater outfall. Based on the new UWWTD, tertiary treatment must be implemented by 2039 to achieve the N- & P-reduction goals. The water reclamation technology of the Spanish P2Green Pilot includes a tertiary treatment to remove suspended solids (including microplastic) > 50 µm and pathogens, while reclaiming the contained nutrients. The tertiary treatment does not contain a targeted removal of pharmaceutical residues, heavy metals or OMP. Depending on the results of WP2, suitable existing removal technologies could be added to the P2Green approach.

6 Consultation process

This chapter refers to the consultation process followed for the elaboration of this Deliverable. As indicated in the Grant Agreement, the blueprints should be developed in a participatory way and a draft document should be shared with local and regional stakeholders to integrate the views of different actors (e.g., feedback on added value, relevant chapters, missing concepts, etc.) including a quadruple helix approach: farmers, authorities, researchers and civil society (e.g., NGOs, associations).

Since the beginning of the project, participatory sessions and workshops organised by different WPs in P2Green have been designed to collect feedback from external stakeholders and identify barriers and drivers, adequate incentives, policy and regulatory reforms, needed alliances, etc. which have been integrated in the blueprints. Examples of the activities organised to collect feedback include stakeholder awareness workshops, focus group interviews, and cross-fertilisation workshops.

In light of this, the 2nd Cross-Fertilisation Workshop of P2Green was organised online in M29 (as part of Task 1.4). The workshop was co-organised by BIOAZUL, S360 and KWB and had 51 participants. Out of all attendees, there were 32 external stakeholders from 6 different countries (i.e., Sweden, Germany, Spain, Italy, Greece, Hungary).

Stakeholders represented researchers, public authorities, farmers and cooperatives, sanitation and waste experts, and innovation-driven SMEs. They were especially interested in exploring how the circular value chains from the three pilot regions could be adapted and replicated in diverse regional contexts.

After the Cross-Fertilisation Workshop, stakeholders were invited to provide feedback on this Deliverable 1.4 in particular, but also on the relevance of blueprints in general. Together with a draft version of this Deliverable, an online survey was provided to the stakeholders to answer specific questions. A total of 12 stakeholders answered the survey providing valuable feedback (anonymously).

Following, the results of the survey and feedback received are presented:

Stakeholder Profile:

1. Which type of stakeholder are you?

General Perception:

2. How useful do you consider the creation of regional blueprints to guide the replication of circular solutions?

3. How relevant are the blueprints developed in P2Green for your own context or expertise?

Content and Structure:

4. Which section of the blueprints do you consider the most relevant?

5. Do you think the level of detail provided is appropriate for understanding and replicating the solutions?

5.1. If you think some chapters/sub-chapters are too detailed, please write down which one/s.

No responses to this question

5.2. If you think some chapters/sub-chapters lack depth, please write down which one/s.

Circular technologies

6. Do the blueprints address key aspects for replication in other regions (e.g. governance, actors, incentives, barriers)?

Replication and Applicability:

7. How feasible would it be to adapt the blueprint solutions in your region or organisation?

8. Which barriers do you see as most limiting for replication in your region? (you can select several barriers)

9. What would be most helpful to support replication of such solutions? (you can select several options)

Engagement and Usability:

10. Were the blueprints clear and easy to understand?

11. Would you recommend this document to peers or colleagues?

12. Would you be interested in taking part in future activities related to the blueprints (e.g. peer review, pilot testing, working groups)?

Based on the answers provided by the 12 stakeholders, the key findings are:

- The majority of respondents (3 out of 4) found the blueprints to be “very useful” for guiding the replication of circular solutions, with 58% of respondents stating they are very clear and easy to understand.
- In terms of personal relevance, 83% of respondents indicated the content was “very relevant” or “somewhat relevant” to their context and expertise.
- Regarding the importance of the chapters included in the report, 75% considered all chapters are equally relevant, while 17% thought Chapter 5 “Circular N&P flow model sand replication potential” was the most important one. These figures suggest the report is cohesively structured.
- The level of detail to understand and replicate the solutions was widely regarded as balanced (67%), while 8% of respondents considered some subchapters lacking depth. It was highlighted that the circular technologies were not sufficiently described. In order to overcome this issue, a specific mention to “Deliverable 1.6 - Progress in set up of pilot regions” (describing the technologies and circular value chains in detail) was included at the beginning of Chapter 4.
- Asked about the inclusion of key aspects for replication in other regions, most stakeholders described the blueprints as “very clear” (42%), while 25% considered the aspects for replication are partially addressed.
- Most respondents (58%) indicated that the adaptation of the blueprint solutions in their regions or organisations would be “feasible but with adaptations”. In contrast, 17% considered it would be “very feasible”, without adaptations.
- In terms of barriers that would limit the replication in their regions, the most relevant barriers identified are:
 - Regulatory uncertainty (58%)
 - Lack of clear business models (50%)
 - Low public or stakeholder acceptance (33%)
 - Lack of funding limitations (33%)
- In light of this, stakeholders emphasised several areas of support needed to facilitate replication:
 - Legal or policy clarification (83%)
 - Funding opportunities (67%)
 - Practical case studies (33%)
 - Local stakeholder engagement tools (33%)

- Training and capacity building (33%)
 - In sum, 75% of respondents would recommend this deliverable to peers or colleagues, while 25% would “maybe” recommend it.
 - With regards to future activities related to the blueprints (e.g., peer review or working groups), 42% is interested in taking part in such activities, while 58% would be “maybe” interested.

More details about the cross-fertilisation approach in P2Green will be included in Deliverable 1.5 – Cross-fertilisation report, due in M46, that will provide more details about the events, workshops and surveys organised, as well as the results from the exchange activities.

7 Conclusions

The development of the blueprints for circular N & P flows in the three pilot regions of Gotland (Sweden), the North German Plain (Germany), and La Axarquía (Spain) represents a significant step towards the realisation of sustainable nutrient management within the P2Green project. This deliverable has outlined the pathways for the uptake and implementation of innovative, bio-based fertilisers derived from human excreta, addressing not only the technical feasibility but also the socio-economic, regulatory, and institutional contexts that will enable the scaling of these solutions.

The state-of-play in each pilot region has demonstrated the critical importance of local context in shaping the implementation of circular nutrient flow models. From Gotland's dependence on imported mineral fertilisers to La Axarquía's pressing challenges with water scarcity and nutrient pollution, the diversity of regional conditions has underscored the need for tailored solutions that reflect each region's environmental, economic, and social realities.

Key findings from this deliverable highlight the following:

- Stakeholder engagement is crucial: the co-design and co-implementation approach taken by P2Green has been essential in building trust among stakeholders. The successful collaboration between local authorities, farmers, technology providers, and research institutes has been a cornerstone of this work. The identification and mapping of key actors, and the ongoing dialogue facilitated by the project, are key to creating the momentum needed for market uptake.
- Policy and regulatory frameworks need to evolve: the regulatory landscape for bio-based fertilisers remains fragmented, with many regions facing unclear or outdated frameworks for the use of human-derived nutrients. The Swedish pilot demonstrates the challenges of navigating this legal grey area, while Germany and Spain face complex regulations surrounding wastewater reuse and nutrient recovery. As highlighted, policy reforms are necessary to foster a circular economy for nutrients, and ongoing engagement with EU-level regulations and national policies will be vital for driving change.
- Economic incentives and market readiness: one of the primary barriers identified across all regions is the economic feasibility of implementing these innovative systems on a large scale. While there is growing interest in reducing dependency on mineral fertilisers, cost-competitiveness remains a challenge. The development of business models that integrate incentive structures for both producers and users of bio-based fertilisers will be critical in overcoming this challenge. Governmental subsidies, funding for research and development, and market-driven incentives will help reduce the economic risks associated with these technologies.

- Capacity building and knowledge sharing: the pilot regions have made significant advances in developing knowledge-sharing platforms and capacity-building initiatives. These initiatives ensure that lessons learned from the pilots are disseminated widely and that stakeholders are equipped with the tools and information needed to support the implementation and scaling-up of circular nutrient management systems. The cross-fertilisation efforts facilitated by the project have proven effective in transferring knowledge and fostering collaboration across regions.
- Replication and scalability: one of the central objectives of this deliverable has been to ensure that the systems implemented in the pilot regions are not only sustainable but also scalable and replicable. The blueprints developed here provide a roadmap for scaling these solutions to other regions in Europe. This is especially important in light of the EU's sustainability goals, which emphasise resource efficiency and the reduction of nutrient pollution.

In conclusion, the blueprints from the three pilot regions provide a comprehensive framework for the adoption and implementation of innovative circular nutrient flows across Europe. The lessons learned from Gotland, the North German Plain, and La Axarquía highlight the importance of regional adaptation, multi-stakeholder engagement, and supportive policy frameworks in ensuring the successful scaling of these solutions.

Moving forward, continued collaboration, advocacy for policy reform, and the development of business models that integrate economic incentives will be key to advancing the widespread adoption of these sustainable and circular approaches to nutrient management.

Next steps will also include the close collaboration with WP6 (Communication, Exploitation, Dissemination) to transform the content of these blueprints into visually attractive brochures and tailored communication materials. These outputs will aim to make the key insights, strategies, and regional pathways more accessible to a broader audience, including policymakers, practitioners, and regional stakeholders. The materials will be finalised and disseminated at a later stage of the project and will be made available through the "P2Green Innovation Platform"⁹.

⁹ P2Green Innovation Platform, available at <https://p2green.eu/open-sources/>

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